

Deliverable 3.3

Chemical composition of the pre- and probiotic halophyte protein

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Executive Summary

The report is structured into four main parts, focusing on:

- 1) Introduction
- 2) Assessing and optimizing halophyte juice for probiotic–protein production.
- 3) Developing sustainable processes for producing sugar-rich halophyte-based media.
- 4) Valorising halophyte-derived hydrolysates into probiotics and postbiotics through mixed-culture fermentation.

Within the halophyte-based biorefinery framework, fresh *Salicornia ramosissima* was fractionated into green juice and green fibres. The juice was used both as a buffer in enzymatic hydrolysis and as a fermentation medium, while the fibres were processed for polyphenol extraction. This deliverable is focused on employing the juice for probiotic fermentation and as a hydrolysis buffer for pre-treated halophyte fibres. Lignified and green fibres were pre-treated to release fermentable sugars, supporting probiotic culture growth.

Initial trials using *S. ramosissima* juice as a fermentation medium for lactic acid bacteria (LAB) yielded mixed results. However, supplementing lactic acid bacteria-fermented juice with yeast markedly improved performance, enabling complete nutrient utilization. These results confirmed that halophyte juice, particularly in mixed cultures, is a nutrient-rich and effective fermentation medium.

Enzymatic hydrolysis of water-extracted fibres revealed that the biomass's lignocellulosic structure was highly recalcitrant, resulting in low sugar yields. Introducing a mild soaking–extraction pre-treatment cycle significantly enhanced fibre convertibility, enabling efficient saccharification without synthetic chemicals or harsh conditions. Moreover, using halophyte juice as a hydrolysis buffer produced sugar yields comparable to those achieved with synthetic buffers, highlighting its dual functionality.

Sugar-rich hydrolysates obtained from juice and pre-treated fibres were subsequently used for microbial cultivation with both single yeast cultures and LAB–yeast mixed cultures. Co-cultivation improved nutrient utilization, minimized unwanted by-products, and increased product yields. Notably, although hydrolysates from synthetic buffers contained higher sugar concentrations, they generated lower microbial biomass compared to those produced using halophyte juice, further underscoring the juice's value as both buffer and nutrient source.

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In conclusion, this document demonstrates the significant potential of halophyte biomass, particularly juice and pre-treated fibres, for sustainable biorefinery applications. The development of LAB–yeast mixed fermentation systems confirmed that halophyte-derived media can support robust microbial growth, efficient nutrient use, and high-quality probiotic production. The dual capability of halophyte juice to function as both a fermentation medium and a hydrolysis buffer proved to be a significant advantage.

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Acronyms and Abbreviations

AB	Acetate Buffer
ANOVA	Analysis of Variance
C5 / C6	Five-carbon / six-carbon sugars
CHNS / CHNS/O	Carbon–Hydrogen–Nitrogen–Sulphur (\pm Oxygen) elemental analysis
CP	Crude Protein
CDW / DCW	Cell Dry Weight / Dry Cell Weight
DAD	Diode Array Detector
DM	Dry Matter
DWC	Dry Weight Concentration
EH	Enzymatic Hydrolysis
Eq.	Equation
FPU	Filter Paper Units (enzyme activity)
GJ	Green Juice
HPLC	High-Performance Liquid Chromatography
HSD	Honest Significant Difference
LAB	Lactic Acid Bacteria
MLR	Multiple Linear Regression
MRS	de Man–Rogosa–Sharpe medium
N/A	Not Applicable
NPCF	Nitrogen-to-Protein Conversion Factor
NS	Natural Solvent
PCs / PC1 / PC2	Principal Components / component 1 / component 2
PCA	Principal Component Analysis
PEC	Protein-Enriched Concentrate
PF	Pre-treated Fibres
PLS	Partial Least Squares
PTFE	Polytetrafluoroethylene
RF	Raw Fibres
RID	Refractive Index Detector
SAH	Strong Acid Hydrolysis
TPC	Total Phenolic Content
TS	Total Solids

1. Introduction

Global agricultural and industrial systems face increasing pressures from climate change, soil degradation, freshwater scarcity, and the expansion of salinized land (Khondoker *et al.*, 2023; Negacz *et al.*, 2022). At the same time, demand for sustainable food, feed, energy, and health-promoting products continues to rise, driving interest in alternative biomass resources and integrated biorefinery approaches (Chen *et al.*, 2023; Gautam *et al.*, 2026). Conventional crop-based systems rely heavily on fertile land and freshwater, creating competition between food and non-food uses and limiting long-term sustainability. In this context, halophytes are emerging as promising supercrops due to their high diversity and exceptional ecological adaptability (Bazihizina *et al.*, 2024). Although halophytes represent only about 1% of global flora, their ability to grow on saline and marginal lands unsuitable for conventional agriculture allows them to avoid competition for fertile soil and freshwater (Accogli *et al.*, 2023). This trait positions halophytes as valuable components of climate-resilient and regenerative agricultural systems.

Beyond their agronomic advantages, halophytes are increasingly recognized by the food, health, and cosmetic industries for their high content of bioactive compounds—including phenolics, flavonoids, carotenoids, vitamins, and antioxidants—which exhibit antioxidant, antimicrobial, and anti-inflammatory activities (Chaturvedi *et al.*, 2021; Giordano *et al.*, 2021; Hulkko *et al.*, 2023). Despite this potential, direct utilization of halophytes as food or feed remains limited. Mature halophyte biomass becomes increasingly lignified, and high salt content complicates consumption. Consequently, substantial amounts of biomass remain underutilized, highlighting the need for efficient valorization strategies. Integrated biorefinery approaches, which combine multiple processing steps to maximize resource efficiency, are particularly well suited for saline biomasses, and the inclusion of bioconversion processes further enhances overall sustainability (Alassali *et al.*, 2017).

Halophyte-based biorefinery systems typically prioritize extraction of high-value bioactive compounds from juiced fibers (Hulkko *et al.*, 2023; Fredsgaard *et al.*, 2023). The remaining lignocellulosic fibers can then be processed into bulk biochemicals (Cybulska *et al.*, 2014; Monção *et al.*, 2022, 2023) and bioenergy (Cayenne *et al.*, 2022), while the liquid fraction (halophyte juice) serves as a substrate for protein-enriched feed (Christiansen *et al.*, 2021). Microbial fermentation has long been recognized as a versatile and sustainable biotechnological tool for upgrading agricultural and industrial biomass into value-added products (Lübeck and Lübeck, 2019). Through the metabolic activities of selected bacteria and fungi, fermentation enables the transformation of complex organic substrates into protein-rich feed ingredients, functional foods, probiotics, and bio-based chemicals that support human and animal health (Sieuwerts *et al.*, 2018; Stadie *et al.*, 2013; Viljoen, 2001; Vorob'eva

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et al., 2016). As global interest in sustainable production systems grows, microbial fermentation is increasingly viewed as a key component of circular bioeconomy strategies, offering opportunities to reduce waste, improve resource efficiency, and diversify product portfolios. Despite these advantages, most current fermentation platforms rely on conventional feedstocks which directly compete with food production and depend on fertile land and freshwater resources (Ritala *et al.*, 2017). Moreover, these substrates often lack the environmental complexity required to promote the selection of robust, stress-tolerant microorganisms with enhanced functional properties. In this context, halophyte biomass represents a promising yet underexplored alternative substrate for probiotic screening and functional fermentation, offering unique physicochemical characteristics that may support the development of resilient and multifunctional microbial cultures.

WP3 within the IGNITION project focuses on the valorization of halophytes, with a particular emphasis on *Salicornia ramosissima*, for the development of sustainable functional probiotic feed additives. As plants adapted to saline soils and requiring minimal freshwater inputs, halophytes represent a promising biomass source for circular biorefinery concepts. Within WP3, lignified *S. ramosissima* biomass is processed to extract high-value bioactive compounds, particularly polyphenols, which are known for their antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and immunomodulatory properties. These extracts are being evaluated for their potential application in aquaculture, where they may enhance nutritional immunomodulation and improve stress resilience in farmed aquatic species (Machado *et al.*, 2024).

Fresh green *S. ramosissima* biomass is fractionated into juice and pulp fibers in accordance with green biorefinery principles. Green juice is utilized as a multifunctional process stream to produce probiotics, postbiotics, and protein-rich fractions, with the aim of developing functional feed additives. In parallel, the green pulp undergoes extraction using methods analogous to those applied to lignified biomass. The residual plant fibers are subsequently subjected to enzymatic hydrolysis to release fermentable sugars, which are used to support probiotic cultivation and protein production within the green juice matrix. To address this, an innovative, sustainable pretreatment was introduced in the WP3 that reduces lignocellulose recalcitrance while repurposing halophyte juice as a hydrolysis medium via a novel soaking-extraction cycle. This mild pretreatment significantly improved fiber convertibility, enabling efficient saccharification without harsh chemicals. Remarkably, halophyte juice as a hydrolysis buffer produced sugar yields comparable to those achieved with synthetic buffers, demonstrating its dual functionality.

The resulting sugar-enriched hydrolysates were used for microbial cultivation with both single lactic acid bacteria (LA) fermentations and LAB–yeast co-cultures. The tested strains—*Lactobacillus plantarum* DSM 13272, *Lactobacillus paracasei* P 4155, *Lactobacillus*

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amylovorus ATCC 33620, *Lactobacillus salivarius* BC 1001, and *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*—were selected based on their well-established fermentation performance and documented probiotic functionality. Lactic acid bacteria (LAB), together with generally recognized as safe (GRAS) yeasts, represent some of the most extensively characterized probiotic microorganisms and are widely applied in functional foods and dietary supplements (Czerucka *et al.*, 2007; Hugot *et al.*, 2023). Previous studies have demonstrated that halophyte biomass supports LAB and yeast growth (Cybulska *et al.*, 2014; Alassali *et al.*, 2017; Hulkko, 2023; Maoloni *et al.*, 2022), and LAB fermentation can recover up to 80% of crude protein from various plant juices (Santamaría-Fernández *et al.*, 2017, 2019b). In *S. ramosissima*, protein recoveries of 60–63% via LAB fermentation and up to 82% via direct acidification have been reported (Hulkko, 2023). Notably, *L. plantarum* DSM 13272 and *L. salivarius* BC 1001 are particularly effective for microbial acidification of green juice (Thomsen and Kiel, 2008b).

WP3 revealed that mixed LAB–yeast cultures consistently outperformed monocultures, enhancing nutrient conversion, reducing undesired by-products, and improving overall productivity. Interestingly, hydrolysates prepared with halophyte juice supported higher microbial biomass formation than those prepared with synthetic buffers, despite lower sugar concentrations, emphasizing the nutritional advantages of halophyte-derived media.

Overall, WP3 demonstrates the substantial potential of halophyte biomass for integrated and sustainable biorefinery applications. The successful implementation of LAB–yeast co-cultivation systems confirm the feasibility of producing high-quality probiotic biomass from halophyte-derived substrates, with halophyte juice emerging as a key multifunctional resource within the process chain. Despite the promising potential of *S. ramosissima* biomass for plant-based probiotic production, expanding the investigation to a broader range of halophytic and marine plant species is warranted. Characterizing their nutritional composition, prebiotic properties, and ability to support diverse probiotic strains could enhance the selection of optimal feedstocks. Simultaneously, exploring novel co-cultivation strategies and increasing microbial strain diversity may improve nutrient recovery, bioactive compound production, and probiotic functionality. Genetic enhancement of probiotic microbes to improve salt tolerance could further facilitate growth and metabolic activity under the high-salinity conditions typical of halophytes. Additionally, comprehensive life cycle assessments are needed to evaluate the environmental and economic sustainability of saline plant-based probiotic production. Addressing these gaps could establish halophyte-derived probiotics as a sustainable, economically viable approach, contributing to the nutraceutical industry while promoting environmental conservation.

In summary, by combining advances in halophyte-based biorefinery processing with aquatic animal health research performed by partners, the IGNITION project contributes to the

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development of robust and circular aquaculture systems that align animal welfare with environmental sustainability. The knowledge and technologies generated in WP3 are expected to inform the design of next-generation functional feeds and integrated health management strategies for the aquaculture industry.

2. Probiotic protein production from *Salicornia ramosissima* juice via lactic acid bacteria acidification and subsequent *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* fermentation

2.1. Introduction

Upcycling of non-food grade plants or their parts based on green biorefinery includes fractionation via screw-press into a liquid fraction, referred to as green juice, and a fibre fraction, referred to as press cake (Chaturvedi *et al.*, 2020; Höltinger *et al.*, 2014). Plant juice is commonly used for protein (Santamaría-Fernández and Lübeck, 2020) and organic acids (Thomsen and Kiel, 2008) production, while juiced fibres in the form of press cake are applied in bulk chemicals, biogas, and fodder production (Höltinger *et al.*, 2014; Parajuli *et al.*, 2015; Prieler *et al.*, 2019).

In general, multiple techniques, including heat coagulation (Christiansen *et al.*, 2021; Damborg *et al.*, 2020), ultrafiltration (Bals and Dale, 2011; Huft *et al.*, 2023), and isoelectric precipitation by direct acidification (Betschart and Kinsella, 1973; Damborg *et al.*, 2020; Nissen *et al.*, 2022) or microbial acidification (Nissen *et al.*, 2022; Santamaría-Fernández *et al.*, 2017, 2019a, 2019b), have been established for the extraction of proteins from plant juice fractions. Isoelectric precipitation relies on the isoelectric point, referring to the pH value at which proteins carry no net charge (positive and negative charges are equal), achieving minimal solubility in aqueous solution. The optimal pH at which the isoelectric point is attained for the majority of protein in green juice varies depending on the plant species and origin. However, optimal protein precipitation is typically observed between pH 3.2 to 6.5 (Santamaría-Fernández and Lübeck, 2020).

Microbial acidification by lactic acid bacteria (LAB) fermentation presents a promising and sustainable approach for protein extraction (Lübeck and Lübeck, 2019). Lactic acid bacteria (LAB) fermentation operates on a similar principle to direct acidification, although pH reduction is achieved through lactic acid production by bacterial metabolism of available sugars rather than by adding concentrated acid. Santamaría-Fernández *et al.* (2017) achieved crude protein (CP) recovery of 67% from red clover juice, 52% from clover grass juice, 39% from alfalfa juice, and 44% from oilseed radish juice through acidification to pH levels ranging from 4.1 to

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4.3 using *Lactobacillus salivarius* fermentation. Furthermore, Santamaría-Fernández *et al.* (2019b) reported CP recoveries reaching up to 79-83% from chicory juice, 72-80% in red clover juice, and 76-86% in timothy juice through acidification to pH levels ranging from 3.8 to 4.1 using *L. salivarius* fermentation. Nissen *et al.* (2022) presented a CP recovery of 63% using *L. salivarius* along with a protease inhibitor, and a 50% recovery with *L. salivarius* alone from alfalfa green juice. Moreover, fermentation was conducted with endogenous alfalfa microorganisms, yielding comparable CP recoveries, suggesting that protein coagulation likely resulted not solely from pH alteration but possibly from other factors like fermentation by-products and secondary metabolites, as pointed out previously by Godessart *et al.* (1987).

In the case of protein precipitation from halophyte juice, Christiansen *et al.* (2021) performed heat coagulation on *Salicornia bigelovii* juice, resulting in a CP recovery of 53%. Hulkko (2023) demonstrated protein extraction from the green juice of *S. ramosissima* and *Tripolium pannonicum* through heat precipitation, acidification with HCl, *L. plantarum* fermentation, and *L. salivarius* fermentation. The highest CP recovery of 82% was achieved with HCl acidification to pH 3.5, followed by 63% with *L. plantarum*, and 62% for both heat coagulation and *L. salivarius* fermentation after pre-treating *S. ramosissima* juice. However, protein precipitation from *T. pannonicum* juice showed poor outcomes, with CP recovery ranging from 37% to 13% for all methods.

When comparing direct acidification with LAB fermentation, fermentation emerges as the preferred method as it eliminates the need for chemicals like inorganic acids and organic solvents, which could limit the scalability of the process due to increased risks associated with storing and handling of hazardous materials. Moreover, LAB are generally recognized as safe (GRAS) and have been shown to have probiotic properties that are beneficial for overall animal health (Florou-Paneri *et al.*, 2013; Hulkko, 2023). Moreover, the produced lactic acid may lower the total amount of feed needed for the same animal growth as indicated by Khan and Iqbal (2016). Protein-enriched concentrate (PEC) derived from plant juice has been shown to result in high-quality feed, considering the comparable content of essential amino acids to conventional animal feeds like soybean (Santamaría-Fernández *et al.*, 2019b, 2017), making it a desirable organic substitute. Nevertheless, LAB fermentation can lead to protein hydrolysis due to LAB proteases, which may negatively affect protein extraction efficiency (Nissen *et al.*, 2022). Additionally, the prolonged duration of the process, in comparison to other methods, may lead to proteolysis mediated by plant proteases.

The present study explored protein extraction through LAB fermentation from halophyte *S. ramosissima* juice. Eight LAB strains were screened for their acidification and protein precipitation properties using both raw and sterilized juice. Control trials, as well as trials involving acidification with supplemented lactic acid were, conducted for comparison.

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Subsequent experiments involved spiking halophyte juice with glucose to match the sugar levels of commercial culture media and fermenting it with selected LAB strains. To recover residual sugar and nitrogen from the fermented broth, it was further fermented with GRAS and the probiotic microorganism *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* (Staniszewski and Kordowska-Wiater, 2021), thereby enhancing overall protein (nitrogen) recovery and quality of PEC in the form of single-cell protein. Figure 1 illustrates a schematic diagram detailing the methods used for protein recovery from *S. ramosissima* juice.

Figure 1: Process diagram for initial screening experiments for protein recovery.

2.2. Materials and methods

2.2.1.

The first batch of green biomass of *S. ramosissima* was cultivated and collected on the 9th and 10th of October 2023 by Riasearch, Portugal (40° 73' 84" N, 8° 66' 18" W). The second batch of *S. ramosissima* was cultivated and collected on the 25th of May 2020 by Les Douceurs du Marais, France (47° 34' 93" N, 2° 49' 43" W). The halophyte biomass was fractionated at the demonstration-scale grass processing facility, Aarhus University in Foulum, Denmark. On the same day, the produced green juice was stored at -20°C until use. The first batch was used in flask trials, and the second batch was used to prepare the fermentation medium in the 2-L bioreactor.

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Figure 2: A) *S. ramosissima* from 2024; B) Fractioned green fibers, C) Collected *S. ramosissima* juice after fractionation.

As fermentative organisms, *Lactobacillus plantarum* DSM 13272 (*L. plantarum*), *Lactobacillus paracasei* P 4155 (*L. paracasei*), *Lactobacillus amylovorus* ATCC 33620 (*L. Anylovorus*), *Lactobacillus salivarius* BC 1001 (*L. salivaris*), and *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* (commercial dry yeast, Malteserkors trgær, De Danske Spritfabrikker A/S, Denmark) were used. In addition, internally isolated strains of *Lactobacillus delbrueckii* (*L. delbrueckii*), *Lactococcus lactis* (*L. lactis*), *Lactobacillus casei* (*L. Casei*), and *Lactobacillus pentosus* (*L. pentosus*) were also employed, however, these isolates have not yet been assigned commercial or culture collection codes. These organisms were selected due to their GRAS status and reputation as common probiotics. Additionally, *Lactobacillus plantarum* DSM 13272 and *Lactobacillus salivarius* BC 1001 have been demonstrated as promising strains for microbial acidification of green juice (Thomsen and Kiel, 2008b). LAB strains were stored on MRS (De Man–Rogosa–Sharpe) agar at 4 °C. For inoculum preparation, the bacterial cultures were transferred to liquid MRS broth and incubated for 18-24 hours at 37 °C and 150 RPM under anaerobic conditions. In case of *L. lactis* the incubation temperature was 30 °C. *S. cerevisiae* was used in freeze-dried form and did not require pre-inoculation before cultivation on juice.

Eight LAB strains were screened for their acidification and protein precipitation properties using both raw and sterilized *S. ramosissima* juice. Control trials and trials involving acidification with lactic acid were conducted for comparison. Additional experiments involved glucose supplementation to match commercial culture medium sugar levels, followed by fermentation with selected LAB strains. To utilize residual sugar and nitrogen from the fermented broth, sequential fermentation with *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* was performed, enhancing protein recovery and the quality of protein-enriched concentrate (PEC).

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2.2.2. Protein precipitation/production from halophyte juice

S. ramosissima juice was thawed at 4 °C for two days and autoclaved at 121 °C for 15 minutes for sterilization. Three techniques were applied to extract crude protein (CP) from sterile and raw juice: 1) direct acidification by lactic acid, 2) lactic acid bacteria (LAB) fermentation, and 3) endogenous fermentation. To directly acidify juice, 90% lactic acid (VWR) was added dropwise using a Pasteur pipette into 100 mL of juice while monitoring the pH continuously with a pH meter (Metrohm 913 pH Meter) until the desired pH of 4 or 3.5 was achieved. In the case of LAB fermentation, 90 mL of juice in a 250 mL Erlenmeyer flask was inoculated with 10 mL of overnight pre-grown LAB culture in MRS broth, flushed with nitrogen for 10 seconds to eliminate air, and incubated in a shaking incubator (KS 4000 ic Control Shaker, IKA) under anaerobic conditions at 37 °C and 130 rpm for 20 hours, except for *L. lactis*, which was incubated at 30 °C. For endogenous fermentation, 100 mL of raw juice in a 250 mL Erlenmeyer flask was incubated under the same conditions as LAB fermentation. Another set of experiments was conducted with glucose-spiked juice. Specifically, 1 L of raw juice was supplemented with 20 g of glucose (VWR) and, when necessary, autoclaved at 121 °C for 15 minutes. Two methods were used to recover protein from both sterile and raw juice supplemented with glucose: 1) LAB fermentation and 2) LAB fermentation followed by *S. cerevisiae* fermentation. LAB fermentation was performed under the same conditions as described previously. Regarding the subsequent fermentation by yeast of LAB fermented juice, 50 mL of fermented juice in a 250 mL Erlenmeyer flask was inoculated with 0.10 g of *S. cerevisiae*, sealed using caps equipped with PTFE membranes, and incubated under aerobic conditions at 30 °C and 130 rpm for 20 hours.

Following protein precipitation, a sample was transferred into a 50 mL Falcon tube and centrifuged (SL 16 Centrifuge, Thermo Fisher Scientific) at 4500 rpm for 15 minutes to separate protein paste and slurry (brown juice). Brown juice was discarded into a new 50 mL Falcon tube and used to measure the pH. To analyse sugars, lactic acid, and ethanol, 5 mL of brown juice was diluted with 20 mL of Milli-Q water and filtered through 0.22 µm syringe filters into HPLC vials. The protein paste was used to obtain and quantify biomass production by drying it at 60 °C until a constant weight was achieved, followed by weighing it on the analytical balance. Control samples (raw and autoclaved juice) underwent the same procedure, except for the absence of the protein precipitation method. For storage, the samples and residual material were kept at -20 °C.

Another set of experiments was conducted with glucose-spiked halophyte juice. 1 L of batch 1 juice was supplemented with 20 g of glucose (VWR) and fermented, or the juice was supplemented with 20 g of glucose and then autoclaved at 121 °C a for 15 minutes. This was

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done to investigate the influence of autoclaving on the subsequent fermentation step and protein precipitation. Two methods were used to recover protein from sterile and raw juice with added glucose: 1) LAB fermentation and 2) LAB fermentation followed by *S. cerevisiae* fermentation. LAB fermentation was performed under the same conditions as described previously in Section 2.3. For the subsequent yeast fermentation of LAB-fermented juice, 50 mL of fermented juice in a 250 mL Erlenmeyer flask was inoculated with 0.10 g of *S. cerevisiae*, sealed using caps equipped with PTFE membranes, and incubated under aerobic conditions at 30 °C and 130 rpm for 20 hours. The precipitates were used to quantify dry matter (DM) and CP recoveries, and the supernatants were used for HPLC analysis.

2.2.3. 2-L Bioreactor fermentation

In the case of halophyte juice spiked with glucose, 2 L of halophyte juice was supplemented with 40 g of glucose and autoclaved at 121°C for 15 minutes. A total of 1.4 L of sterilized juice was added to a 2 L bioreactor (Biostream International B.V). The bioreactor was operated with BioBench (Biostream International B.V). Prior to cultivation, the pH sensor (EasyFerm Bio HB Arc 225, Hamilton Bonaduz AG) and the O₂-dissolved sensor (VisiFerm DO Arc 225, Hamilton Bonaduz AG) were calibrated and set. Subsequently, the bioreactor was flushed with nitrogen to remove residual oxygen from the halophyte juice, and 10 mL of anti-foam was added. The prepared bioreactor was inoculated with 200 mL of an overnight pre-grown *L. lactis* culture in liquid MRS medium. The cultivation conditions were 30 °C, 150 rpm, at the original pH of the juice and under anaerobic conditions. The three 30 mL samples were taken using a 100 mL syringe into 50 mL Falcon tubes at 0, 2, 4, 8, 12, and 24 hours into the cultivation, and if necessary, frozen at -20°C. The LAB fermentation in bioreactors is shown in Figure 3.

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Figure 3: A) Initiation of cultivation with *L. lactis*; B) After acidification with *L. lactis*.

Subsequently, the bioreactor was inoculated with 2.1 g of freeze-dried *S. cerevisiae*. The cultivation conditions were set at 30 °C with 50% dissolved oxygen (dO₂) aeration, regulated by a cascade based on changes in rpm. Three 30 mL samples were taken using a 100 mL syringe and transferred into 50 mL Falcon tubes at 2, 4, 8, 12, and 24 hours into the cultivation. If necessary, the samples were frozen at –20 °C. The samples were then centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 10 minutes. Supernatants were used for analysis of sugar, ethanol, and organic acids, while pellets were washed with 30 mL of Milli-Q water and centrifuged again. The washed cells were then used to determine DM and CP recovery by drying them at 60 °C and weighing on an analytical balance.

2.2.4. 100-L Bioreactor fermentation

Approximately 100 L of halophyte juice was defrosted for two days at room temperature. The bioreactor was operated with BioPilot (Biostream International B.V) (Figure 4A). Prior to filling the bioreactor (Figure 4B), the pH sensor and the O₂-dissolved sensor were calibrated and set. The vessel was filled with 80 L of green juice and 1.6 kg of table sugar (sucrose), simulating hydrolysed halophyte fibre sugars, and sterilized at 121 °C for 40 minutes. After the temperature reached 37 °C, the bioreactor was inoculated with 2 L of an overnight-grown *L. plantarum* culture in liquid MRS media. The cultivation conditions were 37 °C, 200 rpm, with the original pH of the juice and anaerobic conditions. After 15 h of anaerobic fermentation with *L. plantarum*, the conditions of cultivation were changed to 30 °C and 30% dO₂ aeration.

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Aeration was regulated by a cascade based on stirring (rpm). Subsequently, the bioreactor was inoculated with 65 g of freeze-dried *S. cerevisiae*. The cultivation was stopped after 8 hours of aerobic cultivation and 23 hours of total operation time. Samples of 500 mL were taken at the beginning of cultivation, before yeast inoculation, and at the end of cultivation. The samples were processed and analysed as described in the previous subsections. Lastly, the broth was transferred into a collection vessel (Figure 4 C), and microbial cells and solids were left to sediment overnight. The separated solids were removed into the container and dried at 60 °C, while the liquid fraction was frozen at -20 °C.

Figure 4: A) BioPilot (Biotstream International B.V.), B) 100-L bioreactor, C) Sedimentation tank.

2.2.5. Chemical characterization

The dry matter (DM), also known as total solids (TS), and the ash content were determined in samples based on the analytical method developed by the National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL) (Sluiter, 2008a, 2008b).

A CHNS elemental analyser (Pekin Elmer 2400 series CHNS/O) was used to analyse the carbon, hydrogen, nitrogen, and sulphur content of the samples. The method was used as described in Rudnyckyj *et al.* (2025, 2024b). The total protein content was calculated based on the nitrogen content using a nitrogen-to-protein conversion factor (NPCF). The NPCF is 6.25, as all proteins are assumed to have a 16% (w/w) nitrogen content (Mariotti *et al.*, 2008).

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This NPCF value is not an exact figure but represents a well-accepted, widely used approximation. The nitrogen-to-protein conversion is calculated as follows:

$$N \cdot NPCF = P$$

where N is nitrogen content % (w/w) in the dried sample, NPCF is the mass ratio of nitrogen to protein of 6.25, and P is Protein content % (w/w) in the dried sample.

Sugars, organic acids, and ethanol were analysed using high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC; 1260 Infinity II, Agilent Technologies). For total sugar determination, samples were dried at 60 °C overnight and, if needed, ground using a porcelain mortar or knife mill (GRINDOMIX GM 200, Retsch). Strong acid hydrolysis (SAH) was performed to identify the total sugar content using the analytical protocol developed by NREL (Sluiter *et al.*, 2008c). The characterization of ethanol and organic acids followed the analytical protocol established by NREL (Sluiter *et al.*, 2006). Due to the high concentration of organic compounds in the material, liquid samples were diluted fivefold with Milli-Q water. The diluted samples were filtered through 0.22 µm syringe filters into HPLC vials for analysis. Sugars (glucose, cellobiose, xylose, and arabinose), ethanol, acetic acid, and formic acid were analysed using a Bio-Rad Aminex HPX-87H column with 0.005 M H₂SO₄ as the mobile phase and a refractive index detector (RID). Malic and lactic acids were quantified using a 0.2% (v/v) H₃PO₄ mobile phase and diode array detection (DAD).

HPLC results (g/L) were converted to g/100 g DM as described in Alassali *et al.* (2017) and Nwobi *et al.* (2015). A hydration factor of 0.90 was used to estimate glucan content from glucose concentration, and a factor of 0.88 was applied to convert pentoses into xylan and arabinan equivalents.

2.2.6. Statistical methods

All trials were performed in replicates, and the samples were prepared in random order. Results are presented as mean values ± standard deviation. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used for the analysis of experimental results with single or multiple independent variables. The significance level was set to 0.05 for all statistical tests. When necessary, ANOVA was followed by Tukey's Honest Significant Difference (HSD) test. Multiple Linear Regression (MLR) was performed to analyse optimization experiments with multiple factors in response surface methodology. The MLR outcomes are presented graphically as 2D contour plots, showing the dependence of response (dependent variable) on the factors under optimization (independent variables). Correlation analysis was performed to investigate linear association between all factors. Pearson's correlation coefficient (r) was used to quantify these associations, with (r) ≥ 0.7 indicating a strong correlation.

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2.3. Results

2.3.1. Green juice composition

The composition of *S. ramosissima* juice 1 and 2 applied in this study is tabulated in Table 1.

Table 1: The chemical composition of *S. ramosissima* juice is presented in g/100 g of dried juice, except metals are presented in mg/100 g of dried juice.

Component	Halophyte juice 1	Halophyte juice 2
	g/100 g DM Salts (mg/100 g DM)	g/100 g DM Salts (mg/100 g DM)
Total sugars	3.78±0.15	9.63±0.12
Glucan	0.75±0.09	4.57±0.03
Xylan	1.65±0.05	3.00±0.08
Arabinan	1.38±0.04	2.05±0.02
Crude protein	10.2±0.2	11.5±0.9
Ash	29.4±0.4	54.5±3.7
Aluminum	16±6	21±5
Calcium	395±19	1398±226
Magnesium	770±7	2033±39
Phosphorus	156±1	1069±10
Potassium	3550±42	6158±96
Sodium	1367±87	15707±1218

The DM for the fresh juice was 11.6% (w/w) with a pH of 5.17 for halophyte juice 1, and 8.14% (w/w) with a pH of 6.13 for halophyte juice 2. Based on composition analysis, it could be concluded that halophyte juice 1 is low in sugars, which may be a limiting factor for LAB acidification. Despite the relatively high ash content of Juice 1, the corresponding salt concentration is only 3.4% (w/v), whereas Juice 2 contains a higher salt concentration of 4.4% (w/v). In both cases, these salt levels should not cause considerable microbial inhibition, but it may cause a salting-in effect, thus decreasing protein precipitation efficiency.

2.3.2. DM and CP recovery after lactic acid and lactic acid bacteria acidification

The initial investigation focused on identifying the most prominent LAB strain for green juice acidification by comparing its DM and CP recovery in PEC with direct acidification using lactic acid and control samples. Additionally, the study examined the impact of sterilization on LAB fermentation and protein recovery in PEC. Based on the results for controls shown in Figure 5, it can be suggested that autoclaving increases solubilisation of proteins and overall dry

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matter, resulting in lower protein precipitation. However, for fermented juices, the sterilization step yields mixed results. While some LABs show no significant variations in recoveries, others, such as *L. delbrueckii* and *L. lactis*, exhibit substantial differences in both DM and CP recovery. The CP recovery ranges from 27% to 45% for LAB fermented raw juice, 20% to 40% for LAB fermented sterilized juice, 38% to 39% for lactic acid acidification to pH of 4 and pH of 3.5, and 24% after cultivation with endogenous microbiota.

Figure 5: Protein precipitation with lactic acid, lactic acid bacteria (LAB) strains, and endogenous microbiota.

Analysis of variance showed that the precipitation method did not significantly affect CP recovery but had a significant effect on DM recovery (F-value = 10.2; P-value = 2.13×10^{-6}). Subsequently, Tukey's HSD test revealed that only samples that were treated with lactic acid and *L. lactis* had a statistically significant difference in DM recovery compared to the other samples. An N-way ANOVA test was performed to assess the effect of sterilization and LAB strain on CP and DM recovery. The results indicated that neither the LAB strain nor the sterilization step individually significantly influenced CP and DM recovery. However, the test revealed that the interaction of sterilization and LAB stain has a significant combined effect on the CP and DM recovery.

Furthermore, changes in pH and lactic acid production were investigated Figure 6 showing that all LAB fermentations resulted in the desired drop in pH, mostly to pH of 4, along with the lactic acid production, compared to controls and endogenous microbiota (Figure 6). No considerable variation in pH between LAB-fermented samples were observed, except for those treated with *L. lactis*, which demonstrated higher pH than other samples. In addition, sugar analysis showed that *L. delbrueckii*, *L. plantarum*, *L. paracasei*, and *L. amylovorus* fully

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consumed the available sugars in both sterilized and raw juice, suggesting that LAB acidification is limited by the sugar content present in the juice.

Figure 6: pH and lactic acid in control samples and after cultivation with LAB and endogenous microbiota.

The N-way ANOVA test confirmed that LAB acidification and sterilization significantly affected pH, both individually and in combination. Nonetheless, when considering solely the impact of the LAB strain, Tukey's HSD test showed that only samples fermented by *L. lactis* exhibited a significant deviation in pH. Similar to pH, the concentration of lactic acid was significantly different between *L. lactis* and other strains, such as *L. pentosus* and *L. delbrueckii*. Overall, there is no significant difference in acidification among the LAB strains, except for juice fermented with *L. lactis*. These findings support the idea of the limited sugar content in the halophyte juice constrains acidification and, consequently, protein precipitation.

Additionally, correlations between pH, lactic acid concentration, CP recovery, and DM recovery were investigated, revealing a strong correlation between DM and CP recovery, as well as between pH and lactic acid concentration. However, no correlation was observed between pH and/or lactic acid concentration with DM and CP recovery. The results suggest that there are other, unidentified, factors influencing protein precipitation.

2.3.3. DM and CP recovery after LAB acidification and yeast fermentation

Based on results from the abovementioned subsection 2.2.2, it was anticipated that low sugar content in juice may be a limiting factor for acidification, thus for protein precipitation. To address this, halophyte juice was spiked with glucose, resulting in a final sugar concentration of 24 g/L. Initially, the spiked juice was subjected to LAB acidification using selected strains,

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chosen for their ability to consume sugars from the juice completely and their robustness when exposed to both autoclaved and raw juice conditions.

Figure 7A illustrates protein precipitation from spiked juice. The findings reveal that acidification by *L. plantarum*, *L. delbrueckii*, and *L. paracasei* resulted in decreased DM and CP recoveries in sterilized juice compared to raw juice. Conversely, *L. lactis* and *L. amylovorus* cultivated on sterilized juice exhibited considerably higher DM and CP recoveries than on raw juice. When comparing these results with those for the same LAB strains in Figure 5, it can be suggested that the additional glucose led to a reduction in DM and CP recoveries. Moreover, *L. lactis* shows an opposite trend for DM and CP recoveries between juice with and without added glucose.

Investigation of fermentation broths on pH, lactic acid, and sugars Figure 8 demonstrated a high content of residual glucose after LAB fermentation (Figure 8). To utilize the remaining sugar, *S. cerevisiae* was applied to produce single-cell protein, thus increasing overall protein recovery (Figure 7B). In the case of CP recovery, after sequential fermentation of LAB and *S. cerevisiae*, it is important to note that recovered protein in PEC is a combination of protein precipitation by LAB acidification and single-cell protein production through nitrogen assimilation from hydrolysed proteins and nitrogen salts during yeast growth. For consistency in reporting, both the protein precipitation and production are presented as CP recovery. The results in Figure 7B illustrate that sequential fermentation of LAB-fermented broths by yeast led to a considerable increase in DM and CP recoveries for all samples. Particularly noteworthy is the extraordinary CP recovery observed in PEC samples with sterilized juice, ranging between 65% and 101% (w/w), with the lowest CP recovery attributed to *L. plantarum* and the highest to *L. lactis*. The PEC samples with raw juice demonstrated lower CP recoveries with fewer deviations, ranging between 43% and 52% (w/w). Moreover, the smaller differences in DM recoveries between sterile and raw juice, coupled with larger variations in CP recovery, highlight the fact that PEC from sterile juice possesses a higher crude protein content.

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Figure 7: A) DM and CP recovery from glucose-spiked *S. ramosissima* juice after LAB acidification and B) DM and CP recovery from glucose-spiked *S. ramosissima* juice after LAB acidification followed by *S. cerevisiae* fermentation.

In addition, the N-way ANOVA test confirmed the statistical significance of LAB strain, sterilization, and the application of *S. cerevisiae*, along with the combined effect of LAB strain and sterilization with *S. cerevisiae* fermentation on CP recovery in PEC. Subsequently, Tukey's HSD of individual factors showed that only sterilization and *S. cerevisiae* fermentation have a significant effect on protein precipitation.

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Figure 8: A) pH in glucose-spiked *S. ramosissima* juice after LAB acidification followed by *S. cerevisiae* fermentation; B) Lactic acid concentration in glucose-spiked *S. ramosissima* juice after LAB acidification followed by *S. cerevisiae* fermentation; C) Residual glucose in glucose-spiked *S. ramosissima* juice after LAB acidification followed by *S. cerevisiae* fermentation.

2.3.4. 2-L bioreactor cultivation of *L. lactis* followed by *S. cerevisiae*

Based on the results in subsection 2.2.3, it was decided to scale up the cultivation of *L. lactis* with subsequent yeast fermentation up to a 2-L bioreactor. As shown in Figure 9, LAB acidification had no effect on DM or CP recovery. The pH drop did not result in an increase in CP recovery, which is in line with results from flask trials. Moreover, 47% (w/w) of CP could

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be recovered just by centrifugation. The yeast fermentation exhibited gradual CP recovery from 2 hours into the process and reaching 104% (w/w) by 12 hours. The CP recovery exceeding 100% can be attributed to minor water evaporation. Interestingly, between 12 and 24 hours of yeast cultivation, deacidification occurred; however, the pH increase from 4 to 5.5 did not appear to have any significant effect.

Figure 9: DM, CP recoveries, and pH during *L. lactis* and yeast cultivation on halophyte juice 2.

Figure 10 shows the concentration of sugar, DM, CP, and microbial metabolites during cultivation. Based on the measured concentrations, it can be confirmed that the dry concentrate weight and CP concentration began to increase, while glucose consumption started after yeast inoculation. Moreover, ethanol production occurred despite the cultivation being performed with aeration. This may be due to inhibitory environments such as low pH, high solids content, or high glucose levels, which can shift yeast metabolism to anaerobic respiration. However, after 24 hours of yeast cultivation, both ethanol and lactic acid were utilized, confirming the presence of oxygen during cultivation, as yeast cannot utilize these two compounds under anaerobic conditions. Overall, these findings suggest that CP recovery is primarily driven by yeast cultivation, most likely due to cell formation during the process.

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Figure 10: 2-L bioreactor cultivation of *L. lactis* followed by *S. cerevisiae*. A) DCW, CP, and glucose concentration in broth; B) glucose, xylose, lactic acid, and ethanol concentrations during cultivation.

2.3.5. 100-L bioreactor cultivation of *L. plantarum* followed by *S. cerevisiae*

Halophyte juice 2 was fermented with *L. plantarum* followed by *S. cerevisiae* in a 100-L bioreactor. *L. plantarum* was chosen for its robustness and fast utilization of carbon sources. As shown in Figure 11A, CP recovery increased from 40% to 55% (w/w) after 15 hours of anaerobic fermentation with LAB and further increased to 64% (w/w) after 8 hours of aerobic cultivation with yeast. DM recovery remained similar throughout, suggesting an increasing amount of protein in the precipitate during cultivation, which is desirable.

Interestingly, Figure 11B shows that all glucose was consumed by *L. plantarum*, in contrast with the results in subsection 2.2.4 where *L. lactis* did not utilize a significant amount of glucose. Moreover, after 8 hours of aerobic fermentation with yeast, 7.8 g of ethanol/L of juice

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was measured, aligning with the results from the 2-L bioreactor experiment. Additionally, despite LAB consuming all glucose, the yeast was still able to grow and produce ethanol. This could be explained by the presence of other carbon sources, such as fructose, which were not measured.

Figure 11: 100-L bioreactor cultivation of *L. plantarum* followed by yeast fermentation. A) CP and DM recovery; B) pH, glucose, lactic acid, and ethanol concentrations during cultivation. 15 hours of cultivation with *L. plantarum* is also the time point when the bioreactor was inoculated with the yeast.

2.4. Discussion and conclusion

The analysis of *S. ramosissima* juice revealed a sugar content of 3.8 g/100 g DM, equivalent to 4.4 g of sugar/L of juice, and a crude protein content of 10.2 g/100 g DM, corresponding to 11.8 g of crude protein/L of juice for halophyte juice 1. For halophyte juice 2, the analysis showed a sugar content of 9.6 g/100 g DM, equivalent to 7.8 g of sugar/L of juice, and a crude protein content of 11.5 g/100 g DM, corresponding to 9.4 g of crude protein/L of juice. The relatively low amount of sugar was identified as a limiting factor during fermentation, particularly LAB acidification, as evidenced by statistically insignificant variations in CP recovery for all LAB strains (Figure 5), and the total utilization of glucose in juice by all LAB strains with exception of *L. lactis*. This finding served as the main reason for spiking halophyte juice with glucose to reach a sugar concentration above 20 g/L, which is the approximate sugar content in MRS medium commonly used for LAB cultivation. Consequently, the final sugar concentration in the glucose-spiked juice amounted to 24 g/L for halophyte juice 1 and 28 g/L for halophyte juice 2. Moreover, a high content of salts of 3.4 % (w/v) and 4.4 % (w/v), respectively, mainly consisting of potassium, sodium, and calcium, was found in juices. It is suggested that this considerable salt content may influence protein solubility, causing a salting in/out effect, but the exact impact on protein precipitation is unknown.

The preliminary trial involving halophyte juice 1, including control samples and samples acidified with lactic acid, demonstrated that direct acidification with lactic acid to pH levels of

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4 and 3.5 led to an enhancement in CP recovery by 8% and 9%, respectively, compared to the controls. This underscores that acidification causes protein precipitation in halophyte juice, even though the increase in CP recovery is not particularly substantial, which could be explained by the high solubility of the proteins present. The investigation of sterilized and raw juice showed that autoclaving results in loss of DM and CP in PEC, suggesting that heat treatment results in plant fibre and crude protein disintegration, thus increasing solubility. However, sterilization and pH reduction (acidification) by LAB fermentation, did not show a significant impact on protein precipitation, except for fermentation with *L. lactis*. For this strain, a significant decrease in CP and DM recovery was observed following the sterilization of the juice. The contrasting outcomes observed in *L. lactis* fermented samples compared to other LAB strains may be attributed to the lower optimal temperature for *L. lactis* (30°C) relative to the other strains, which have an optimal temperature of approximately 37°C.

The lack of significant impact from LAB acidification on protein precipitation in green juice, coupled with the absence of correlation between pH reduction and CP and DM recovery in LAB-treated samples, suggests that other factors may be constraining the process. The probable cause could be proteases, given that LABs are recognized for secreting extracellular proteases, which effectively break down plant proteins (Christensen *et al.*, 2022; Lim *et al.*, 2019). The reduction of the protein size is associated with the higher solubility of the protein (Pereira *et al.*, 2016). Nissen *et al.* (2022) showed that using protease inhibitors during *L. salivarius* acidification of alfalfa green juice led to a 19% boost in CP recovery. The experiments, including LAB acidification of glucose-supplemented green juice (Figure 7A) demonstrated decreased DM and CP recovery, which may be attributed to an increased production of proteases. Nonetheless, the precise cause remains unidentified. Similar to the results of the initial trial, LAB acidification had no significant impact on DM and CP recovery from halophyte juice. Moreover, no correlation was observed between pH reduction and CP and DM recovery in PEC, leading to the same conclusion.

The subjugation of LAB-fermented juices to *S. cerevisiae* fermentation resulted in considerable protein recovery from the juice (Figure 7B). The analysis showed that yeast was able to consume all glucose and partially utilize lactic acid, increasing pH as a result, as presented in Figure 8. The fermentation of *S. cerevisiae* with LAB offers numerous advantages: 1) both are GRAS and are considered probiotics (Khushboo *et al.*, 2023; Salminen *et al.*, 1998; Staniszewski and Kordowska-Wiater, 2021), 2) they typically have a symbiotic relationship (Xu *et al.*, 2021), 3) both produce highly digestible protein with an excellent amino acid profile (Erdman *et al.*, 1977; Yamada and Sgarbieri, 2005), and 4) *S. cerevisiae* has the capability to metabolize lactic acid as a carbon source, thus minimizing resource loss (Zeng *et al.*, 2023). Additionally, the relatively rapid growth of *S. cerevisiae*

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confirms that LAB-fermented juice is rich in readily accessible protein, suggesting that the proteins present in the juice are likely hydrolysed and highly soluble, hence resistant to protein precipitation by LAB acidification. This observation aligns with previous results showing no correlation between pH reduction and protein precipitation. Interestingly, sterilization proved to be a significantly impactful step for protein recovery through LAB fermentation followed by yeast fermentation, resulting in 22 to 58% higher CP recovery compared to raw juice. This is possibly due to increased competition with microorganisms present in raw juice under aerobic conditions, as well as enhanced hydrolysis after autoclaving juice.

The scaled-up process to a 2-L bioreactor (

Figure 10) confirmed that LAB acidification (drop in pH) did not contribute to protein precipitation and demonstrated that CP recovery mainly comes from yeast cultivation. These results further support the idea that the proteins present in halophyte juice are highly soluble and accessible for enzymatic hydrolysis (EH) by microbial proteases and subsequently yeast assimilation. The pilot trial with a 100-L bioreactor showed similar outcomes. However, LAB acidification positively influenced protein recovery, leading to a 15% increase in CP recovery. Further investigations are required, as this was an initial trial to test the suitability of the 100-L bioreactor for PEC production.

In conclusion, the findings of this study highlight the efficient utilization of *S. ramosissima* juice for the production of protein concentrate through microbial acidification and yeast fermentation. Based on this results, it was concluded that the LAB acidification and the sterilization step alone have little to no effect on protein separation. Moreover, no correlation between pH reduction and CP recovery was observed, suggesting that other factors are in play in increasing protein solubility.

Furthermore, supplementation of halophyte juice with glucose showed similar outcomes for LAB fermentation, with no significant difference between the LAB stains used for CP recovery. However, subsequent *S. cerevisiae* fermentation of LAB-fermented resulted in considerable improvement in protein recovery, especially after sterilization of juice, with final CP recovery of 92% for *L. delbrueckii*, 95% for *L. paracasei* P 4155, and 101% for *L. lactis*, respectively.

Lastly, experiments with a 2-L bioreactor showed that the main and possibly only contributor to protein production is yeast cultivation. However, due to the well-established probiotic benefits of LAB, their use should be maintained in subsequent trials.

Overall, these findings underscore the potential of halophyte juice as a viable substrate for PEC production through the synergistic advantages offered by the combined fermentation processes involving LAB and yeast. The resulting protein concentrate could serve as an excellent fish feed additive, thus contributing to ecological farming and food security.

3. Low input pre-treatment of *Salicornia ramosissima* lignocellulose for high enzymatic convertibility

3.1. Introduction

Current pre-treatment methods for lignocellulose often rely on unsustainable practices. Hence, in this study, we present a greener alternative that uses subcritical-water excitation at mild temperatures, combined with hydrothermal liquid derived from extracted halophyte lignocellulose as a natural catalyst (product patented by Aalborg Universitet, id: 82456DK01). This approach eliminates the need for organic solvents and chemicals, contributing to the circular economy of halophyte-based biorefineries. Additionally, enzymatic saccharification of lignocellulose typically requires synthetic buffers, such as 5 mM acetate buffer (Larran *et al.*, 2015; Smichi *et al.*, 2016) or 50 mM citrate buffer (Ansari *et al.*, 2021; Batog *et al.*, 2021; Dash *et al.*, 2023). To address this, we propose halophyte juice slurry as a viable alternative, which in this study achieved comparable saccharification yields to the commonly used 5 mM acetate buffer.

In summary, this work introduces an innovative and sustainable pre-treatment method to reduce the recalcitrance of halophyte lignocellulose while simultaneously repurposing halophyte juice as a medium for enzymatic hydrolysis (EH), as illustrated in Figure 12. This technology significantly lowers production costs, supports a sustainable economy, and advances the commercialization of halophytes.

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Figure 12: Graphical overview of experimental workflow for optimizing halophyte fibres saccharification.

3.2. Materials and Methods

3.2.1. Halophyte biomass materials

Green and lignified biomasses of *S. ramosissima* were used in the present study. The green biomass was described in section 2.2.1. The first batch of halophyte lignified biomass was derived from lignified *S. ramosissima* obtained from Riasearch, Portugal in October 2020. The second batch was also sourced from Riasearch, produced in November 2021. The plants were cultivated in a sandy soil bed within an open greenhouse, allowing them to produce seeds before harvesting. After harvesting, the lignified plants were air-dried in mesh trays in the shade before shipping. The third batch of halophyte lignified biomass was provided by Seawater Solutions, Scotland. It was produced in saline soil in the Andalusia region, Spain, and irrigated with seawater. The lignified plant biomass was shipped in November 2023. Before storage and use, all lignified plant materials were rinsed with water, dried at room temperature, and reduced to pieces smaller than 2 cm using an agricultural straw shredder (AM55, J. N. Jensen og Sønner, Agerskov, Denmark). The dried, shredded biomass was then stored at room temperature.

3.2.2. Pre-treatment of halophyte fibres

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The pre-treatment of lignified and juiced green halophyte biomasses was based on subcritical water extraction and soaking in a liquid catalyst patented by AAU (id: 82456DK01). During pre-treatment optimization, since soaking alone had no effect, all investigated samples underwent at least one extraction, with or without a soaking step. For instance, *S. ramosissima* biomasses that underwent a single extraction step without soaking were used as control samples. The extraction step was performed using subcritical water extraction at 130 °C for 1 hour with a 5% (w/v) biomass loading in demineralized water. This process served a dual purpose: extracting bioactive compounds and acting as a pre-treatment for the halophyte lignocellulose material. The soaking step involved immersing the halophyte fibres at varying temperatures of 20 °C, 40 °C, 60 °C, and 80 °C for 30 minutes. The soaked fibres were then sieved using a 0.2 mm metal screen to remove residual liquid catalyst, which was subsequently reused in the next soaking steps. The pre-treatments were carried out in a 10 L reactor (Nordic Engineering ApS) with a maximum volume loading of 8 L. The soaking liquid catalyst serves as the green catalyst for halophyte lignocellulose pre-treatment during the extraction/pre-treatment step.

The optimized and established pre-treatment protocol for lignified fibres involved two extraction steps at 130 °C for 1 hour, using a 5% (w/v) biomass loading in demineralized water. An intermediate soaking step with a liquid catalyst was carried out at room temperature for 30 minutes prior to the second extraction. For juiced green fibres, Soxhlet extraction with water was performed for 4 hours, followed by a 30-minute soaking step at room temperature. The final step involved subcritical water extraction at 130 °C for 1 hour, using a 5% (w/v) biomass loading in demineralized water. Finally, the pre-treated fibres were saccharified by EH.

3.2.3. Enzymatic hydrolysis

For EH, Cellic® CTec3 was used. The pre-treated *S. ramosissima* biomass was dried at 60 °C until completely dry, which took approximately 2-3 days. The hydrolysis was performed with solids loading of 10% (w/w) and enzyme dosage of 20 or 30 FPU/g of lignocellulose biomass. A 0.05 M acetate buffer at pH 5 was used as the medium for hydrolysis. The samples were incubated at 50 °C and 150 rpm for 24 hours. Additionally, *S. ramosissima* juice and its slurry were investigated for EH on pre-treated halophyte fibres. The procedure followed the same method as described above, with one modification: instead of using a 0.05 M acetate buffer, *S. ramosissima* juice or its slurry at different pH levels was used as the saccharification medium. After incubation, the hydrolysates were transferred into two 50 mL Falcon tubes, with one stored at -20 °C. The samples were centrifuged at 4500 rpm for 15 minutes. Then, 5 mL of supernatant was carefully pipetted into new 50 mL Falcon tubes and diluted with 20 mL of

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Milli-Q water. The diluted hydrolysates were then filtered using 0.22 μm syringe filters and transferred into HPLC vials for sugar content analysis. For storage, the HPLC vials containing filtered hydrolysates were stored at $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$

3.2.4. Chemical and statistical analysis

Chemical characterization and statistical analysis of the results was performed as described in the section 2.2.6 and 2.2.5, respectively.

3.3. Results

3.3.1. Lignified halophyte and green juice composition

In the present study, green and lignified biomasses of *S. ramosissima* were applied, and their compositions are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: The chemical composition of *S. ramosissima* juice, juice slurry, lignified straw batch 1, batch 2, and batch 3 is presented in g/100 g of dried biomass.

Components	S. <i>ramosissima</i> juice (g/100 g DM of raw juice)	S. <i>ramosissima</i> juice slurry (g/100 g DM of raw juice)	S. <i>ramosissima</i> biomass batch 1 (g/100 g DM of raw biomass)	S. <i>ramosissima</i> biomass batch 2 (g/100 g DM of raw biomass)	S. <i>ramosissima</i> biomass batch 3 (g/100 g DM of raw biomass)
DM % (w/w)	8.14	5.90	95.8	95.0	95.0
Total sugars	9.63 \pm 0.12	N/A	40.7 \pm 7.6	54.7 \pm 0.4	47.1 \pm 3.4
Glucan	4.57 \pm 0.03	N/A	21.5 \pm 3.9	31.4 \pm 0.3	26.4 \pm 1.4
Xylan	3.00 \pm 0.08	N/A	15.4 \pm 3.1	23.4 \pm 0.1	17.5 \pm 2.4
Arabinan	2.05 \pm 0.02	N/A	3.83 \pm 0.55	N/A	3.05 \pm 0.65
Klason-lignin	11.0 \pm 0.1	5.47 \pm 0.29	14.8 \pm 0.3	16.6 \pm 0.1	44.3 \pm 1.3
Crude protein	11.5 \pm 0.9	4.80 \pm 0.10	7.18 \pm 0.16	5.52 \pm 0.31	5.50 \pm 0.70

Green juice was used directly as medium for the EH of pre-treated halophyte fibres or centrifuged at 4500 rpm for 15 minutes to separate solid paste and slurry. The resulting halophyte juice slurry was then used as medium for the EH of pre-treated halophyte fibres. Additionally, *S. ramosissima* juice was fermented with *L. plantarum* DSM 13272 at $37\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 150 rpm for 24 hours to assess the suitability of fermented juice as a medium for EH.

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3.3.2. Experimental design of the enzymatic hydrolysis of pre-treated halophyte fibres

The pre-treated *S. ramosissima* biomass was dried at 60 °C until completely dry, which took approximately 2-3 days, except for sample 2.80.2.2 (wet fibres), which was used directly for enzymatic saccharification. Table 3 lists the sample names along with the corresponding pre-treatments used on *S. ramosissima* lignocellulose biomass batch 1 and batch 2 prior to EH.

Table 3: Overview of pre-treated *S. ramosissima* samples of batch 1 and 2 investigated for enzymatic hydrolysis. NS (natural solvent).

Sample name	Extraction	Soaking	Type halophyte straw	Soaking liquid
C1	1 x extraction	No	Batch 1	-
C2	No	No	Batch 2	-
20.1	1 x extraction	1 x soaking at 20°C	Batch 1	Halophyte-based NS
40.1	1 x extraction	1 x soaking at 40°C	Batch 1	Halophyte-based NS
60.1	1 x extraction	1 x soaking at 60°C	Batch 1	Halophyte-based NS
80.1	1 x extraction	1 x soaking at 80°C	Batch 1	Halophyte-based NS
80.2	1 x extraction	1 x soaking at 80°C	Batch 2	Halophyte-based NS
20ML	1 x extraction	1 x soaking at 20°C	Batch 2	Mangrove leaf-based NS
20MS	1 x extraction	1 x soaking at 20°C	Batch 2	Mangrove stem-based NS
2.80.1	2 x extraction	1 x soaking at 80°C	Batch 1	Halophyte-based NS
1.80.2.2	1 x extraction	2 x soaking at 80°C	Batch 2	Halophyte-based NS
2.80.2.2	2 x extraction	2 x soaking at 80°C	Batch 2	Halophyte-based NS
2.80.2.2 (wet fibres)	2 x extraction	2 x soaking at 80°C	Batch 2	Halophyte-based NS

3.3.3. Effect of soaking temperature on enzymatic hydrolysis of lignified halophyte straw

This experiment was conducted on lignified *S. ramosissima* biomass from batch 1. Although this batch contained some arabinose, it was not reported in the results, as it was either absent in the hydrolysates or present in negligible amounts. The effect of soaking temperature on the enzymatic convertibility of lignified *S. ramosissima* biomass is shown in Figure 13. I

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Figure 13: Enzymatic saccharification of extracted halophyte fibres C1, soaked and extracted at 20, 40, 60, 80 °C, and soaked at 80 °C and two times extracted. A) hydrolysis yield in % (g of released sugar/g of total sugar in pre-treated fibres); B) concentration of free sugar in L (litre) of hydrolysate.

In general, halophyte lignocellulose is highly recalcitrant, as evidenced by the control sample C1, which resulted in a negligible amount of xylose after hydrolysis. Soaking at 20 °C significantly improved enzymatic saccharification, achieving over 60% hydrolysis yield for both glucan and xylan. However, soaking liquids derived from mangrove leaves and stems showed substantially lower saccharification compared to halophyte-based soaking liquids and were therefore excluded from further screening.

Overall, the results indicate that increasing the soaking temperature enhances the amount of hydrolysed sugars, suggesting that soaking pre-treatment has a positive effect on the EH of

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halophyte lignocellulose. For instance, as shown in Figure 13B, at 20 °C, the glucose and xylose concentrations in the hydrolysate were 13.4 g/L and 9.8 g/L, respectively, whereas at 80 °C, they increased to 17.1 g/L and 12.1 g/L. Notably, sample 2.80.1, which underwent a second extraction, showed a slight improvement in hydrolysis yield compared to sample 80.1 (Figure 13A). However, Figure 13 sample 2.80.1 exhibited a significantly higher glucose concentration in the hydrolysate compared to sample 80.1 (Figure 13B). This difference can be explained by variations in the starting material used for hydrolysis: sample 80.1 underwent only a single extraction, whereas sample 2.80.1 was subjected to two extractions. As a result, the glucose concentration was increased in the pre-treated biomass due to the second extraction, while xylose was lost due to hemicellulose degradation during pre-treatment.

Furthermore, the statistical analysis revealed that soaking temperature significantly affected glucan and xylan hydrolysis, with F-values of 10.6 and 10.9 and p-values of 0.005 for both parameters. However, Tukey's HSD test showed that the major difference occurred between soaking temperatures of 20 °C and 80 °C, while differences at other temperatures were too small to be considered statistically significant. Moreover, one-way ANOVA showed no statistically significant difference in hydrolysis yield between samples extracted only after soaking and those extracted both before and after soaking; however, the final glucose concentration in the corresponding hydrolysates differed significantly.

3.3.4. Effects of multiple soaking and extraction on *S. ramosissima* lignocellulose composition

The experiment was conducted on lignified *S. ramosissima* biomass from batch 2. The purpose of this experiment was to assess the amount of glucose, xylose, and lignin released and subsequently lost after each pre-treatment step and biomass handling process, such as transfers between vessels after filtration. From previous experiments, it was observed that glucose tends to become more concentrated in the pre-treated biomass, meaning there is an increase in grams of glucose per 100 g of DM. In contrast, xylose is lost during processing, resulting in a decrease in grams of xylose per 100 g of DM. Lignin also generally becomes more concentrated, but since it is not a targeted polymer during enzymatic saccharification, it was not extensively investigated.

Firstly, to establish mass balances, the mass loss during pre-processing was investigated, as shown in Table 4. It was observed that approximately one-quarter of the biomass was lost after each pre-treatment step. Interestingly, no mass loss was detected during the first soaking. However, after the first extraction, the second soaking resulted in a mass loss of over 24% (w/w), suggesting that pre-treated fibres are more prone to degradation. Additionally, as

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lignocellulose fibres break into smaller pieces, they become more susceptible to loss during soaking and sieving.

Table 4 :Mass loss during pre-treatment and handling of *S. ramosissima* lignocellulose batch 2.

Type of fibre pre-treatment	After soaking and extraction	After two soakings and extraction	After two soakings and two extractions
Mass removal compared to raw fibres% (w/w)	29.4	54.8	73.6

As observed in Figure 14A, glucose becomes enriched in the pre-treated biomass, reaching its highest concentration in the most extensively pre-treated *S. ramosissima* biomass, while xylose and lignin remain at relatively similar levels. By accounting for mass loss and adjusting the sugar content based on the original raw *S. ramosissima* biomass, Figure 14B shows that overall glucose, xylose, and Klason lignin are lost during handling and pre-treatment. However, glucan appears to be the most resistant to removal. As shown in Figure 14C, after the first two pre-treatment steps, over 80% (w/w) of the glucan remains in the biomass, and after the final pre-treatment, nearly 60% (w/w) of the glucan is retained compared to the original lignocellulose. This suggests that with each extraction, approximately 20% (w/w) of the glucan is released. Xylan and Klason lignin follow similar removal patterns, with lignin experiencing higher losses compared to the other sugar polymers. Moreover, the first soaking as a pre-treatment step did not independently contribute to mass loss or the removal of glucan, xylan, or Klason lignin, as evidenced by the Soaked C2 sample in Figure 14.

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Figure 14: Mass balances of glucan, xylan, and Klason lignin in the pre-treated halophyte straw batch
 2. A) Amount of sugar polymer and Klason lignin in the raw and pre-treated halophyte fibres; B) Corrected amount of sugar polymer and Klason lignin in the raw and pre-treated halophyte fibres to original raw halophyte fibre (including mass loss during pre-treatment); C) Percentage of remaining sugar polymer and Klason lignin in halophyte fibres after each pre-treatment corresponding to the original raw fibres.

3.3.5. Effect of multiple soaking and extraction on enzymatic hydrolysis

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In Figure 15, the effect of multiple soaking and extraction cycles, as well as the state of the biomass (wet vs. dried) before EH, were investigated in relation to sugar enzymatic convertibility. Firstly, results demonstrated that each pre-treatment cycle had a significant impact on the saccharification of halophyte lignocellulose, confirming the importance of soaking and extraction as pre-treatment steps. Secondly, an investigation of wet fibres after the final extraction showed similar outcomes to dried fibres, suggesting that using wet fibres directly for saccharification could be a viable option. This approach could eliminate the need for an expensive drying step in large-scale production, unless transportation is required before the saccharification process.

The statistical analysis revealed that the number of soakings and extractions significantly affected glucan hydrolysis, with an F-value of 11.2 and a p-value of 0.03, but had no significant effect on xylan hydrolysis. Moreover, one-way ANOVA showed no statistically significant difference in the saccharification of wet versus dried pre-treated halophyte lignocellulose fibres, confirming that both can be applied in an advanced process without loss of hydrolysis yields.

Figure 15: Enzymatic saccharification of halophyte fibres Batch 2, C2 control, once soaked at 80 °C and once extracted, twice soaked at 80 °C and twice extracted, and twice soaked at 80 °C and twice extracted wet fibres (were not dried after extraction/before enzymatic hydrolysis) A) hydrolysis yield in % (g of released sugar/g of sugar in pre-treated *S. ramosissima* fibres); B) concentration of free sugar in L (litre) of hydrolysate.

3.3.6. Suitability of pre-treated halophyte lignocellulose fibres in media based on synthetic buffer, *S. ramosissima* juice, and its variations

This experiment aimed to assess the suitability of *S. ramosissima* juice, fermented *S. ramosissima* juice, and *S. ramosissima* juice slurry as media for EH, comparing them to the commonly used acetate buffer as a synthetic medium. EH was conducted on lignified *S. ramosissima* biomass from batch 3, which had undergone pre-treatment involving soaking at

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80 °C and two extractions. Additionally, the EH of *S. ramosissima* juice slurry was investigated at different pH levels, as the natural pH of this medium can vary due to ongoing microbial activity, leading to acidification of the slurry.

Figure 16: Enzymatic saccharification of pre-treated halophyte fibres in synthetic buffer, halophyte juice, halophyte juice slurry, and fermented juice. A) hydrolysis yield in % (g of released sugar/g of sugar in pre-treated *S. ramosissima* fibres); B) concentration of free sugar in L (litre) of hydrolysate.

Raw *S. ramosissima* lignocellulose fibres were used as a control.

The results presented in Figure 16A show that the highest glucan hydrolysis was reached in acetate buffer, followed by juice slurry at pH of 5.5, and then halophyte juice. Sugar concentrations in acetate buffer were 28.9 g of glucose, 15.7 g of xylose, and 2.9 g of

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arabinose/L of hydrolysate, followed by juice slurry at pH of 5.5 with 23.7 g of glucose, 14.9 g of xylose, and 2.8 g of arabinose/L of hydrolysate, and by halophyte juice with 23.6 g of glucose, 14.8 g of xylose, and 2.9 g of arabinose/L of hydrolysate. Overall, the major difference in hydrolysis yield was observed in glucan hydrolysis, while other sugar polymers exhibited varying patterns depending on the type of medium used. The lowest saccharification of pre-treated *S. ramosissima* biomass was observed Figure 16 when fermented juice was used as the medium, with glucan and xylan hydrolysis reaching only 35% (w/w) and 50% (w/w), respectively (Figure 16B). This could be attributed to the production of proteases by the lactic acid bacteria, which may have deactivated the enzymes used for hydrolysis.

The ANOVA test, in Table 5, confirmed that type of medium, pre-treatment, and pH have significantly influenced hydrolysis yields of all sugar polymers.

Table 5: N-way ANOVA of influencing factors, including fibre pre-treatment, medium type (synthetic, halophyte juice, and halophyte juice slurry), and medium pH used for enzymatic hydrolysis, with response factors being glucan, xylan, and arabinan hydrolysis.

Factors influencing glucan hydrolysis	F-value	p-value
Fibres pre-treatment	148	1.95×10 ⁻¹⁰
Type of medium	37.4	6.95×10 ⁻⁶
pH	17.1	6.81×10 ⁻⁵
Factors influencing xylan hydrolysis		
Fibres pre-treatment	395	3.51×10 ⁻¹⁴
Type of medium	15.9	0.0004
pH	14.2	0.0002
Factors influencing arabinan hydrolysis		
Fibres pre-treatment	7.52	2.09×10 ⁻⁸
Type of medium	9.00	0.004
pH	36.4	1.27×10 ⁻⁶

Tukey's HSD test revealed that the only statistically significant difference in glucan hydrolysis was between samples hydrolysed in halophyte juice and acetate buffer. This confirms halophyte juice slurry is a more suitable medium for the saccharification of halophyte lignocellulose fibres, as there was no significant difference between using acetate buffer or halophyte juice slurry for EH. Tukey's HSD test also confirmed that pre-treatment significantly affected saccharification, while the pH of the medium had a statistically significant effect on sugar polymer hydrolysis across media types. Furthermore, an in-depth investigation showed that the pH of halophyte juice slurry had no significant effect on glucan hydrolysis. However,

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it had some impact on xylan and arabinan hydrolysis, with F-values of 20 and 6.8 and p-values of 0.002 and 0.03, respectively.

Based on the results, *S. ramosissima* juice slurry appears to be an excellent alternative to synthetic medium for EH. Its use could reduce overall production costs while enhancing the potential of a halophyte-based circular economy by repurposing waste/side streams from halophyte-based biorefineries.

3.3.7. Enzymatic hydrolysis of green fractioned halophyte fibres

The composition of juiced green fibres from *S. ramosissima* was analysed, with results presented in Figure 17. Overall, the composition is similar to that of lignified fibres, with a few notable differences: the green fibres contain higher amounts of arabinan and crude protein, and lower levels of lignin. It is important to note that the total sum of the component percentages is 104.5% (w/w), which can be attributed to standard deviations in both sampling and analytical measurements.

Figure 17: The composition of *S. ramosissima* juiced green fibres. The % (w/w) is based on weight.

The EH of pre-treated and raw juiced green fibres from *S. ramosissima* is presented in Figure 18. Pre-treated samples hydrolysed in acetate buffer (synthetic medium) showed the highest sugar concentration, reaching 33 g/L, equivalent to approximately 62% (w/w) saccharification yield compared to raw fibres. This was followed by pre-treated samples hydrolysed in green juice slurry, yielding 27 g/L of total sugars, or around 51% (w/w) saccharification yield. As expected, raw fibres performed poorly, achieving less than 20% saccharification yield. These results suggest that pre-treatment significantly enhances the EH of green halophyte fibres.

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However, unlike lignified fibres, pre-treated green fibres performed significantly better in synthetic buffer than in juice slurry. This contrasts with findings in previous sections, where no statistically significant difference was observed between the two media, acetate buffer and juice slurry, during hydrolysis of pre-treated lignified fibres.

Figure 18: The results of EH of pre-treated and raw green fibres of *S. ramosissima* with 0.05M acetate buffer and green juice slurry as media. GJ PF: Pre-treated fibres hydrolysed in green juice slurry; GJ RF: Raw fibres hydrolysed in green juice slurry; AB PF: Pre-treated fibres hydrolysed in acetate buffer; AB RF: Raw fibres hydrolysed in acetate buffer.

3.4. Discussion and conclusion

Compositional analysis of *S. ramosissima* lignocellulose confirmed a high polysaccharide content of 41–55 g/100 g DM, while juiced green fibres showed a similar profile with higher arabinan and crude protein, but lower lignin content, compared to lignified fibres. Pre-treatment using a soaking–extraction cycle significantly enhanced EH, mimicking mild acid pre-treatment. It was demonstrated that the combined effect of soaking and extraction played a crucial role in lignocellulose degradation by effectively reducing the lignin barrier, depolymerizing hemicellulose and cellulose, and enhancing enzyme accessibility during saccharification. This was further confirmed by the EH of samples subjected to single and double soaking–extraction cycles.

A double soaking–extraction cycle achieved a hydrolysis yield of up to 90% and a sugar concentration of 64 g/L, outperforming many conventional methods. While EH of green fibres

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also benefited from pre-treatment, the results differed from those of lignified fibres. Specifically, green fibres showed significantly better hydrolysis performance in synthetic buffer compared to slurry media, whereas lignified fibres exhibited similar outcomes in both media. This suggests that the choice of hydrolysis medium may need to be tailored to the specific type of biomass. Additionally, the highest sugar concentration obtained from green fibres was 33 g/L, nearly half of that achieved with lignified fibres.

The integrated use of soaking–extraction, EH, and the natural buffering properties of halophyte juice presents a scalable, low-impact model for halophyte-based biorefineries. Future research should utilize the produced hydrolysates as substrates for microbial conversions to confirm their suitability for such applications, as addressed in the subsequent study within the IGNITION project. Additionally, further work should assess the life cycle impacts and techno-economic feasibility of the process, as well as extend the investigation to other halophyte species or biomass blends to validate the robustness and industrial relevance of the biorefinery concept.

4. Co-cultivation of lactic acid bacteria and fodder yeasts for probiotics and postbiotics production on halophyte-based hydrolysate

4.1. Introduction

In the present study, the focus was on the co-cultivation of probiotic bacteria and yeast on halophyte-based substrate, drawing inspiration from traditional fermented products where these microorganisms coexist in a natural symbiotic relationship. Examples of such products include sourdough (Pérez-Alvarado *et al.*, 2022), kombucha (Antolak *et al.*, 2021), sauerkraut (Yang *et al.*, 2020), fermented vegetables (Seo *et al.*, 2020; Xu *et al.*, 2024), kefir (Stadie *et al.*, 2013), cocoa and coffee fermentation (de Oliveira Junqueira *et al.*, 2019; Figueroa-Hernández *et al.*, 2019), as well as fermented beverages like wine and craft beer (Torres-Guardado *et al.*, 2021). The major benefit of co-culturing lies in this natural symbiosis, which has been demonstrated across various traditional fermentations, enhancing flavour, texture, and probiotic potential. This symbiosis can be attributed to several factors: 1) nutrient exchange: yeasts can produce essential metabolites, such as vitamins and amino acids, that support bacterial growth, while bacteria, in turn, can provide carbon sources and growth-promoting factors for yeasts (Ponomarova *et al.*, 2017; Sieuwerts *et al.*, 2018; Stadie *et al.*,

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2013; Viljoen, 2001); 2) enhanced stress tolerance: the presence of both microorganisms can improve their resilience to environmental stresses, such as acidity, osmotic pressure, and oxidative stress, which is particularly beneficial in fermentation processes (Sieuwerds *et al.*, 2018; Stadie *et al.*, 2013; Viljoen, 2001; Vorob'eva *et al.*, 2016); 3) modulation of metabolism: the interaction between bacteria and yeasts can influence metabolic pathways, leading to improved utilization of carbon sources and enhanced production of bioactive compounds (Nguyen *et al.*, 2015; Sieuwerds *et al.*, 2018); 4) enhanced postbiotics production: co-cultivation can enhance the production of antimicrobial peptides, organic acids, and exopolysaccharides, which contribute to gut health and the stability of fermented products (Cheirsilp *et al.*, 2003; González-Orozco *et al.*, 2023; Healy *et al.*, 2023; Pihurov *et al.*, 2023). By leveraging these advantages, mixed microbial culture processes present a promising strategy for enhancing the functionality and stability of probiotic and postbiotic formulations, particularly when utilizing halophyte-derived substrates.

More specifically, Healy *et al.* (2023) demonstrated that Kombucha SCOBY (Symbiotic Culture of Bacteria and Yeast) cultivated on saline plant-based feedstocks exhibited enhanced production of organic acids, including lactic, tartaric, and acetic acids, compared to pure cultures of *S. cerevisiae* and *L. plantarum*. Similarly, González-Orozco *et al.* (2023) found that *Lactobacillus kefiranofaciens* showed increased survival and postbiotic production when co-cultured with *Kluyveromyces marxianus*. In another study, Liu *et al.* (2019) reported that the co-culture of *Bacillus coagulans* and *C. utilis* exhibited significantly enhanced growth and nutrient utilization compared to individual cultures when cultivated on *Lactobacillus* fermentation wastewater. Wang *et al.* (2023) demonstrated that mixed fermentation with *L. plantarum*, *Bifidobacterium animalis* subsp. *lactis*, and *C. utilis* enhanced fermentation quality compared to control groups, leading to an increased content of bioactive compounds and a reduced fermentation time. Furthermore, incorporating yeast into bacterial fermentation may enhance the product's digestibility and improve its essential amino acid profile (Salgado *et al.*, 2021; Zhang *et al.*, 2017).

Based on the demonstrated symbiotic relationship in previously reported research, various GRAS yeast species, including *S. cerevisiae*, *K. marxianus*, *C. jadinii*, and *Y. lipolytica*, along with probiotic bacteria *B. coagulans* and *L. plantarum*, were selected to evaluate their ability to utilize carbon sources and grow on halophyte-based media. Additionally, parameters such as lactic acid, acetic acid, vitamin B12, and crude protein concentration were analysed to assess their potential for probiotic and postbiotic production, as these compounds have demonstrated overall health benefits and are considered nutraceuticals. Firstly, only yeast strains were cultured in the halophyte-based hydrolysate to assess their performance in a single culture system. Then, various bacteria–yeast co-cultures were investigated, and the

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four best-performing combinations were selected for inoculum size and cultivation time optimization using a full factorial experimental design. The experimental work is summarized in Figure 19. In summary, this study highlights the benefits of bacteria–yeast co-culture on microbial growth and overall postbiotic production using halophyte-based hydrolysate as a medium, identifying key factors contributing to the co-culture's strong performance.

Figure 19: Process diagram for lactic acid bacteria (LAB) and fodder yeasts cultivation experiments.

The figure was made with BioRender.com and adapted from Rudnyckyj *et al.* (2024a).

4.2. Materials and methods

4.2.1. Halophyte biomass

The green biomass of *S. ramosissima* was cultivated and collected on the 9th and 10th of October 2023 by Riasearch. The halophyte biomass was fractionated on the 12th of October 2023 at the demonstration-scale grass processing facility, Aarhus University in Foulum, Denmark. The same day, the produced green juice was stored at -20°C until needed. Before use, green juice was defrosted at room temperature (19 °C) and centrifuged (SL 16 Centrifuge, Thermo Fisher Scientific) at 4500 RPM for 10 minutes to separate solid paste and slurry. Followingly, halophyte juice slurry was used as a media for the enzymatic hydrolysis of pretreated halophyte fibers.

For enzymatic hydrolysis, Cellic® CTec3 (Novozymes A/S) was used as a source of cellulases and hemicellulases, with a specific enzymatic activity of 214 FPU/mL and a density of 1.2

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g/mL. The pretreated *S. ramosissima* lignocellulose was dried at 60 °C until completely dry and then ground into a fine powder using the GRINDOMIX GM 200 (Retsch GmbH, Germany). The enzymatic hydrolysis mixture, with a total weight of 500 g, consisted of 50 g of dried and ground *S. ramosissima* lignocellulose fibers, 5.6 g of enzymatic solution (equivalent to 4.67 mL and 20 FPU/g of lignocellulose biomass on dry matter basis), and 442 g of *S. ramosissima* juice slurry. These components were combined in 1 L shaking flasks using table weights, resulting in a final dry matter loading of 10% (w/w). The flasks were incubated at 50 °C and 170 RPM for 24 hours. After incubation, unhydrolyzed solids were removed by centrifugation (SL 16 Centrifuge, Thermo Fisher Scientific) at 4500 RPM for 10 minutes. The sugar-rich hydrolysate slurry was then used for microbial cultivation, composition analysis, and the remaining sample was stored at –20 °C.

4.2.2. Microbial cultivation on halophyte-based media (shake flasks)

For yeast cultivation on halophyte-based hydrolysate, 90 mL of hydrolysate slurry was added to a 250 mL Erlenmeyer flask, followed by 10 mL of yeast inoculum grown in YPD broth. For *S. cerevisiae*, instead of a liquid inoculum, 0.2 g of freeze-dried cells was added to 100 mL of hydrolysate. The samples were incubated at 32 °C and 150 rpm for 72 hours, except for *K. marxianus* strains, which were incubated at 37 °C. For bacterial and yeast co-cultures on halophyte-based hydrolysate, 90 mL of hydrolysate slurry was added to a 250 mL Erlenmeyer flask, followed by 5 mL of yeast inoculum grown in YPD broth and 5 mL of bacterial inoculum grown in MRS broth. In the case of *S. cerevisiae* and bacterial co-cultures, instead of liquid yeast inoculum, 0.1 g of freeze-dried cells was added to 95 mL of hydrolysate along with 5 mL of bacterial inoculum from MRS broth.

Additionally, control samples containing only hydrolysate were incubated to assess the growth of naturally occurring microorganisms in the *S. ramosissima* biomass. All cultivations were conducted under aerobic conditions, with flasks sealed using caps equipped with PTFE membranes to allow gas exchange. The samples used in co-cultivation are presented in Table 6.

Table 6: Combinations of bacteria and yeast used in co-culture trials, along with the incubation temperatures for each microbial combination and control samples.

Bacterial culture	Yeast culture	Temperature °C
<i>B. coagulans</i> ATCC 7050	<i>K. marxianus</i> DSM 7238	37
<i>B. coagulans</i> ATCC 7050	<i>K. marxianus</i> DSM 70292	37
<i>B. coagulans</i> ATCC 7050	<i>C. jadinii</i> DSM 2361	32
<i>B. coagulans</i> ATCC 7050	<i>C. jadinii</i> DSM 70163	32
<i>B. coagulans</i> ATCC 7050	<i>S. cerevisiae</i>	32
<i>L. plantarum</i> DSM 13272	<i>K. marxianus</i> DSM 7238	37
<i>L. plantarum</i> DSM 13272	<i>K. marxianus</i> DSM 70292	37

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<i>L. plantarum</i> DSM 13272	<i>C. jadinii</i> DSM 2361	32
<i>L. plantarum</i> DSM 13272	<i>C. jadinii</i> DSM 70163	32
<i>L. plantarum</i> DSM 13272	<i>S. cerevisiae</i>	32
Control		32/37

After incubation, the broths were transferred into two 50 mL Falcon tubes, with one stored at -20 °C. The samples were then centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 10 minutes. The supernatants were collected in 50 mL Falcon tubes, while the cell pellets were washed with 30 mL of Milli-Q water and centrifuged again. This washing process was repeated twice. The washed cells were stored at -80 °C overnight, then freeze-dried for three days and used to determine biomass production and crude protein concentration in the broths. Then, 5 mL of the collected supernatant was carefully pipetted into new 50 mL Falcon tubes and diluted with 20 mL of Milli-Q water. The diluted hydrolysates were then filtered using 0.22 µm syringe filters and transferred into HPLC vials for sugar content analysis. For long-term storage, the HPLC vials containing hydrolysates were kept at -20 °C.

4.2.3. Chemical characterization

Dry matter, crude protein, free sugars, organic acids analysis were performed as described in section 2.2.6. Vitamin B12 was quantified via HPLC using an Agilent Poroshell 120 EC-C18 column (4.6 × 100 mm, 2.7 µm) with eluants A) 90% (v/v) MeOH in Milli-Q water (30%) and B) Milli-Q water with 0.6% TFA (70%), analyzed with DAD.

4.2.4. Statistical analysis

All trials were performed as triplicates, and the samples were prepared in random order. All results are given as mean values with standard deviation. The ANOVA test was used for the analysis of experimental results with single or multiple independent variables. The significance level was set to 0.05 for all performed statistical tests. When necessary, ANOVA was supplemented by Tukey's Honest Significant Difference (HSD) test. Second-order Multiple Linear Regression (MLR) was performed for the analysis of optimization experiments with inoculum size and cultivation time, based on response surface methodology. The MLR outcomes are presented graphically in the form of 2D contour plots, showing the dependence of response (dependent variable), including cell dry weight and crude protein concentration, on the factors under optimization (independent variables), involving inoculum size and cultivation time.

The correlation analysis was performed to investigate linear association between all factors. The Pearson's correlation coefficient (r) was used to quantify these associations, with $(r) \geq 0.7$ indicating strong correlation between variables. To further explore patterns and relationships

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within the dataset, Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was employed as an exploratory method. PCA reduces high-dimensional data by transforming the original variable space into a smaller set of latent variables, known as principal components (PCs), which capture the directions of maximum variance in the data. The results of PCA are presented through scores and loadings plots. The scores plot visualizes how individual data points project onto a new coordinate system defined by the principal components, typically using the first two components (PC1 and PC2). The loadings plot illustrates the contribution of each original variable to the principal components, and reveals correlations among variables. Each principal component is characterized by its explained variance, which represents the proportion of the total variance retained in the lower-dimensional space. This approach aids in identifying underlying data structures, while enhancing visualization and interpretation. R version 4.3.1 (R Core Team, 2020), with RStudio software (v. 2024.09.0 Build 375), was used for all statistical analyses. For correlation visualization and PCA, R was supplemented with corrplot package (v. 0.95) (Wei *et al.*, 2024), and mdatools package (v. 0.14.2) (Kucheryavskiy, 2020).

4.3. Results

4.3.1. Yeast cultivation on hydrolysate from lignified fibres

As an initial investigation, halophyte-based hydrolysate was used as a cultivation medium for selected yeast strains to assess its suitability as a substrate for single-culture growth. Based on the results shown in Figure 20, *K. marxianus* DSM 70292, *C. jadinii* DSM 70163, and *Y. lipolytica* DSM 8218 did not consume free sugars in the hydrolysate. However, variations in organic acid levels suggest some utilization of these compounds. Additionally, the higher cell dry weight (CDW) content compared to the hydrolysate indicates that other carbon sources were likely utilized by these strains.

In contrast, *K. marxianus* DSM 7238 and *C. jadinii* DSM 2361 demonstrated excellent utilization of free sugars, except for xylose in *C. jadinii* DSM 2361. Ethanol production was observed in both strains, suggesting a possible oxidofermentative metabolism, despite aerobic cultivation conditions. This could be due to an inhibitory environment in the hydrolysate or the Crabtree effect. Nevertheless, both strains achieved comparable dried cell concentrations of 9.6 g/L and 10.0 g/L, respectively. Another well-performing strain was *S. cerevisiae*, which was able to utilize the majority of available carbon sources. However, since *S. cerevisiae* can only metabolize C6 sugars, it is possible that inherent microorganisms present in the halophyte juice co-grown with the yeast. The achieved CDW was 9.9 g/L, similar to *K. marxianus* DSM 7238 and *C. jadinii* DSM 2361.

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Figure 20: Composition of halophyte-based hydrolysate and broths after cultivation with selected yeast strains, including monomeric sugars, acetic acid, lactic acid, ethanol, and crude protein.

The statistical analysis showed that yeast cultivation had a significant impact on hydrolysate composition. The one-way ANOVA confirmed that the effect of yeast cultivation was statistically significant for sugar, ethanol, and crude protein content. However, there was no significant difference in acetic and lactic acid content between hydrolysate and culture samples. Furthermore, the Tukey HSD test confirmed that samples cultivated with *S. cerevisiae*, *K. marxianus* DSM 7238, and *C. jadinii* DSM 2361 achieved the highest crude protein content, with no statistically significant differences among them. This supports these three strains as potential candidates for yeast cell and postbiotic production.

4.3.2. Screening of co-cultivation of lactic acid bacteria and yeast on hydrolysate from lignified fibres

Based on the results from the previous section, *Y. lipolytica* DSM 8218 was excluded from further investigation due to its poor performance compared to other yeast strains. As shown in Figure 21, there was no considerable sugar consumption or production of organic acids and ethanol in the control samples, indicating minimal or no growth of contaminant microorganisms. However, a small amount of precipitate containing protein was observed. This may be attributed to residual biomass from the hydrolysate that was not completely removed during solids separation or that precipitated during cultivation. Moreover, the protein levels in the control samples were significantly lower than in the cultivated samples, confirming

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that cultivation led to cell growth and protein production. When comparing *L. plantarum* DSM 13272 and *B. coagulans* ATCC 7050, the primary difference was in lactic acid content. Lactic acid was not detected in samples with *B. coagulans* ATCC 7050, suggesting that its production rate was lower compared to *L. plantarum* DSM 13272, or that yeast utilized the lactic acid. Alternatively, the absence of lactic acid may indicate that *B. coagulans* ATCC 7050 did not grow effectively. However, the consumption of xylose and arabinose in the co-culture combination based on *B. coagulans* ATCC 7050 and *S. cerevisiae* suggests that bacterial growth occurred, as the yeast was only able to utilize C6 sugars.

Overall, yeast cultivated with *B. coagulans* ATCC 7050 performed better in terms of CDW and crude protein content compared to those grown with *L. plantarum* DSM 13272. This may be due to lactic acid accumulation inhibiting growth at higher concentrations or to *L. plantarum* DSM 13272 growing more rapidly, thereby limiting yeast growth. However, free sugar was detected in most samples containing *L. plantarum* DSM 13272, suggesting that competition for carbon sources was unlikely to be the limiting factor. The highest cell production was observed with *S. cerevisiae*, *K. marxianus* DSM 7238, and *C. jadinii* DSM 2361 in combination with *B. coagulans* ATCC 7050, achieving CDW of 9.6, 10.6, and 10.2 g/L of broth, respectively, with crude protein concentrations of 4.5, 3.2, and 4.8 g/L. These results align with the findings from previous sections on yeast-only cultivation, supporting the validity of the observed patterns. Additionally, the concentrations of ethanol, formic acid, fructose, and galactose were analysed. Only negligible amounts of these compounds were detected in the samples, with only minor changes observed.

Figure 21: Composition of halophyte-based hydrolysate, control samples incubated at 32 °C and 37 °C, and broths after co-cultivation with bacterial and yeast strains. Parameters include monomeric sugars, acetic acid, lactic acid, cell dry weight, and crude protein content.

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Furthermore, vitamin B12 levels, antioxidant capacity, and TPC were analysed, as shown in Table 7. The results indicate that the control samples exhibited some vitamin B12 production, suggesting the growth of naturally occurring microorganisms in the halophyte biomass. Additionally, a significant difference in vitamin B12 production was observed between samples containing *B. coagulans* ATCC 7050 and *L. plantarum* DSM 13272, indicating that *B. coagulans* ATCC 7050 contributes substantially to vitamin B12 synthesis. Regarding antioxidant capacity, the reduction levels were relatively low across all samples. To be considered a strong antioxidant agent, the reduction in antioxidant capacity should exceed 80%. However, certain co-cultures, such as *S. cerevisiae* with *B. coagulans* ATCC 7050, demonstrated an increase in antioxidant capacity. For TPC, no significant differences were observed between the hydrolysate and fermented broth, suggesting minimal interaction between phenolics in the plant material and the bacterial or yeast strains. However, an increase in TPC between the raw juice and hydrolysate suggests that pre-treatment has a considerable effect on phenolic release. This can be attributed to the impact of pre-treatment on halophyte lignocellulose, which facilitates the breakdown of the lignin fraction, thereby releasing phenolics into the hydrolysate.

Table 7: Content of vitamin B12, Antioxidant capacity, TPC in the raw juice, hydrolysate, controls, and co-cultivated samples

Sample/ Bacterial culture	Yeast culture	Vitamin B12 (mg/L)	Antioxidant capacity (%)	TPC (g/L)
<i>S. ramosissima</i> juice		N/A	16.8±0.6	3.61±0.15
Hydrolysate		N/A	28.2±0.6	13.8±1.2
Control 32°C		0.38±0.02	26.9±1.3	13.2±0.5
Control 37°C		0.44±0.01	28.7±5.0	13.0±0.3
<i>B. coagulans</i> ATCC 7050	<i>K. marxianus</i> DSM 7238	3.13±0.01	34.2±3.3	13.3±1.0
<i>B. coagulans</i> ATCC 7050	<i>K. marxianus</i> DSM 70292	5.60±0.29	33.5±5.9	13.4±0.9
<i>B. coagulans</i> ATCC 7050	<i>C. jadinii</i> DSM 2361	0.65±0.14	39.3±7.6	12.7±0.1
<i>B. coagulans</i> ATCC 7050	<i>C. jadinii</i> DSM 70163	41.4±0.9	41.0±4.6	13.0±0.1
<i>B. coagulans</i> ATCC 7050	<i>S. cerevisiae</i>	4.42±2.70	54.9±6.1	13.7±0.6
<i>L. plantarum</i> DSM 13272	<i>K. marxianus</i> DSM 7238	N/A	39.9±6.8	11.9±0.1
<i>L. plantarum</i> DSM 13272	<i>K. marxianus</i> DSM 70292	N/A	23.4±0.3	14.3±0.2
<i>L. plantarum</i> DSM 13272	<i>C. jadinii</i> DSM 2361	4.10±0.19	23.4±0.4	13.0±0.3
<i>L. plantarum</i> DSM 13272	<i>C. jadinii</i> DSM 70163	N/A	26.4±2.5	13.6±0.9
<i>L. plantarum</i> DSM 13272	<i>S. cerevisiae</i>	N/A	21.1±1.0	12.8±0.1

The N-way ANOVA, shown in Table 8, followed by Tukey HSD, showed that *L. plantarum* DSM 13272 and *B. coagulans* ATCC 7050 had significantly different effects on sugar consumption, vitamin B12 production, acetic acid, and lactic acid levels. However, they had no significant impact on crude protein production and only a limited influence on CDW. While

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bacteria alone had no effect on certain parameters, their interaction with yeast was significant for all measured variables. On the other hand, it seems that yeast culture was the main driver for cell and protein formation. Furthermore, results showed that the type of yeast strain generally had an overall significant impact on cell dry weight, crude protein content, and sugar consumption, except in the case of *K. marxianus* DSM 70292. This strain exhibited the lowest CDW, crude protein production, sugar, and organic acid consumption compared to other yeast strains. Moreover, it was confirmed that *C. jadinii* strains demonstrated the highest organic acid utilization, especially acetic acid, compared to other strains. Based on the results, the most promising bacteria–yeast combinations include *K. marxianus* DSM 7238, *C. jadinii* DSM 2361, *C. jadinii* DSM 70163, and *S. cerevisiae*, with *B. coagulans* ATCC 7050 as the optimal bacterial strain.

Table 8: N-way ANOVA with bacteria, yeast, and their combined effect as influencing factors on the investigated variables

Effect of co-cultures on cell dry weight (CDW)	F-value	p-value
Bacteria	6.67	0.027
Yeast	37.4	5.48×10 ⁻⁶
Bacteria:Yeast	8.68	0.002
Effect of co-cultures on crude protein content		
Bacteria	2.97	0.115
Yeast	15.9	0.0005
Bacteria:Yeast	14.2	0.002
Effect of co-cultures on lactic acid		
Bacteria	6603	1.95×10 ⁻¹⁵
Yeast	969	6.75×10 ⁻¹³
Bacteria:Yeast	969	6.75×10 ⁻¹³
Effect of co-cultures on acetic acid		
Bacteria	6.76	0.03
Yeast	75.2	2.01×10 ⁻⁷
Bacteria:Yeast	3.49	0.05
Effect of co-cultures on Vitamin B12		
Bacteria	1326	5.78×10 ⁻¹²
Yeast	183	2.63×10 ⁻⁹
Bacteria:Yeast	203	1.58×10 ⁻⁹
Effect of co-cultures on sugar consumption		
Bacteria	65.3	1.08×10 ⁻⁵
Yeast	341	1.22×10 ⁻¹⁰
Bacteria:Yeast	41.9	3.23×10 ⁻⁶

4.3.3. Optimization of inoculation size and time of selected yeasts and bacteria co-cultivation on hydrolysate from lignified fibres

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Based on the outcomes presented in previous sections, the decision was reached to conduct a more in-depth study into the effect of inoculum size and cultivation time on cell dry mass and protein production by selected co-cultures based on the combination of *B. coagulans* ATCC 7050 with one of these yeasts: *K. marxianus* DSM 7238, *C. jadinii* DSM 2361, *C. jadinii* DSM 70163, and *S. cerevisiae*. The hydrolysate used in the experiment contained 0.91 ± 0.05 g/L of lactic acid, 0.95 ± 0.01 g/L of acetic acid, a pH of 4.65, and 16.1 ± 0.3 g/L of free sugars. The N-way ANOVA results indicated that inoculum size and cultivation time had a statistically significant impact on cell dry mass and crude protein production across all co-cultures. However, variations in inoculum size had a lesser effect on these response variables in co-cultures involving *C. jadinii* strains. In contrast, co-cultures with *K. marxianus* DSM 7238 and *S. cerevisiae* were more strongly influenced by inoculum size, showing a high level of statistical significance between increased inoculum size and microbial cell and crude protein production.

Moreover, MLR analysis was conducted for each co-culture to further examine the effects of inoculum size and cultivation time on cell dry mass and crude protein production, with the results visualized as contour plots from Figure 22 to Figure 25.

Figure 22: Contour plots based on MLR analysis: A) Effect of inoculum size and time of cultivation on cell dry weight/L of broth with *B. coagulans* ACTT 7050 and *C. jadinii* DSM 2361 co-culture (F-value of 19.8 and R^2 of 0.90); B) Effect of inoculum size and time of cultivation on crude protein/L of broth with *B. coagulans* ACTT 7050 and *C. jadinii* DSM 2361 co-culture (F-value of 20.6 and R^2 of 0.95).

The generated models explain a significant portion of the variability in product concentrations, with an adjusted R^2 ranging from 0.71 to 0.97. For individual microbial combinations, *C. jadinii* DSM 2361 exhibited a quadratic effect, as shown in Figure 22A and Figure 22B. The negative coefficients for the quadratic terms (-1.94 for cell dry mass concentration and -0.74 for crude

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protein production) in the MLR model suggested that while increasing cultivation time initially enhances production, excessive durations lead to a decline. This decline is likely due to resource depletion, accumulation of metabolic by-products, or other environmental limitations. Based on these findings, the optimal cultivation time for *C. jadinii* DSM 2361 appears to be between 2.5 and 3 days' post-inoculation.

Figure 23: Contour plots based on MLR analysis: C) Effect of inoculum size and time of cultivation on cell dry weight/L of broth with *B. coagulans* ACTT 7050 and *C. jadinii* DSM 70163 co-culture (F-value of 7.1 and R^2 of 0.75); D) Effect of inoculum size and time of cultivation on crude protein/L of broth with *B. coagulans* ACTT 7050 and *C. jadinii* DSM 70163 co-culture (F-value of 6.0 and R^2 of 0.71).

Figure 24: Contour plots based on MLR analysis: E) Effect of inoculum size and time of cultivation on cell dry weight/L of broth with *B. coagulans* ACTT 7050 and *K. marxianus* DSM 7238 co-culture (F-value of 22.0 and R^2 of 0.96); F) Effect of inoculum size and time of cultivation on crude protein/L of broth with *B. coagulans* ACTT 7050 and *K. marxianus* DSM 7238 co-culture (F-value of 68.3 and R^2 of 0.97).

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For other microbial combinations, the relationship between inoculum size, cultivation time, and products was more linear, with higher inoculum sizes and longer cultivation times generally resulted in increased cell and crude protein yields, with the optimal cultivation time extending beyond 72 hours, as shown in Figure 23 to Figure 25. Notably, the highest product concentrations were observed in co-cultures of *B. coagulans* ATCC 7050 with *K. marxianus* DSM 7238 (Figure 24) and *S. cerevisiae* (Figure 25), achieving 17.5 g of CDW and 6.9 g of crude protein/L of broth and 16.5 g of CDW and 6.3 g of crude protein/L of broth, respectively. These maximum yields were attained at the highest inoculum level 10% (v/v) after the longest cultivation time point of 72 hours.

Figure 25: Contour plots based on MLR analysis: G) Effect of inoculum size and time of cultivation on cell dry weight/L of broth with *B. coagulans* ACTT 7050 and *S. cerevisiae* co-culture (F-value of 18.3 and R^2 of 0.90); H) Effect of inoculum size and time of cultivation on crude protein/L of broth with *B. coagulans* ACTT 7050 and *S. cerevisiae* co-culture (F-value of 20.2 and R^2 of 0.91).

Moreover, samples were analysed for pH, vitamin B12, remaining free sugars, lactic acid, and acetic acid, with the results presented in Table 9. The decreasing concentrations of acetic and lactic acids across all samples, combined with a steady increase in pH over the cultivation period, suggest that the yeasts present are actively consuming these acids. This indicates their potential for effective deacidification in mixed microbial cultures. For example, in the *K. marxianus* DSM 7238 co-culture, pH increased significantly from 5.13 to 8.41. This rise may be attributed to yeast metabolism shifting towards amino acid consumption once the primary carbon source is depleted, leading to ammonia release and a subsequent pH increase. Overall, a larger inoculum size of 10% (v/v) resulted in higher sugar consumption, greater organic acid utilization, and a more pronounced pH increase compared to lower inoculum

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sizes. Notably, after just 24 hours of cultivation, most free sugars were depleted, particularly in co-cultures with *K. marxianus* DSM 7238 and *S. cerevisiae*.

Table 9: Measured levels of remaining free sugars, lactic acid, acetic acid, and vitamin B12 in the broths after cultivation at various time points and inoculum sizes, following a full factorial experimental design with selected microbial co-cultures.

<i>B. coagulans</i> ACTT 7050 and <i>C. jadinii</i> DSM 2361						
Cultivation time (hours)	Inoculation size bacteria and yeast (%) (v/v)	Remaining free sugars (g/L)	Vitamin B12 (mg/L)	Lactic acid (g/L)	Acetic acid (g/L)	pH
24	1	5.33	2.30	0.28	0.41	4.67
24	10	3.57	6.98	0.08	0.44	5.54
48	5	1.98±0.79	25.3±1.6	0.06±0.04	0.05±0.04	5.59±0.20
72	1	0.95	24.7	0.21	-	5.69
72	10	1.20	20.1	0.13	-	6.80
<i>B. coagulans</i> ACTT 7050 and <i>C. jadinii</i> DSM 70163						
Cultivation time (hours)	Inoculation size bacteria and yeast (%) (v/v)	Remaining free sugars (g/L)	Vitamin B12 (mg/L)	Lactic acid (g/L)	Acetic acid (g/L)	pH
24	1	3.77	-	0.765	0.29	4.84
24	10	2.32	2.95	-	0.06	5.94
48	5	1.66±0.20	27.8±2.5	0.40±0.06	0.09±0.04	5.62±0.42
72	1	1.63	25.7	-	-	5.88
72	10	0.20	25.1	-	-	7.60
<i>B. coagulans</i> ACTT 7050 and <i>K. marxianus</i> DSM 7238						
Cultivation time (hours)	Inoculation size bacteria and yeast (%) (v/v)	Remaining free sugars (g/L)	Vitamin B12 (mg/L)	Lactic acid (g/L)	Acetic acid (g/L)	pH
24	1	2.11	19.9	0.15	1.65	4.76
24	10	1.19	9.56	0.07	1.92	5.13
48	5	0.57±0.12	26.0±11.1	0.09±0.05	1.52±0.09	5.41±0.14
72	1	-	42.2	-	-	6.66
72	10	0.08	-	0.22	-	8.41
<i>B. coagulans</i> ACTT 7050 and <i>S. cerevisiae</i>						
Cultivation time (hours)	Inoculation size bacteria and yeast (%) (v/v)	Remaining free sugars (g/L)	Vitamin B12 (mg/L)	Lactic acid (g/L)	Acetic acid (g/L)	pH
24	1	3.01	5.90	0.03	0.29	5.58
24	10	2.75	6.63	0.11	0.55	5.84
48	5	0.17±0.06	12.1±1.2	0.19±0.02	-	5.86±0.11
72	1	0.17	14.0	0.18	-	6.54
72	10	-	47.5	0.33	-	7.42

However, as shown in Figure 23, Figure 24, and Figure 25, cell growth continues beyond 72 hours, suggesting that microbial cultures are utilizing alternative nutrient sources. Furthermore, sugar utilization was highest in co-cultures with *K. marxianus* DSM 7238 and *S. cerevisiae*, aligning with the highest observed concentrations of CDW and crude protein production. Similarly, these co-cultures exhibited the highest vitamin B12 production after 72

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hours of cultivation, reaching 42.2 mg/L with *K. marxianus* DSM 7238 and 47.5 mg/L with *S. cerevisiae*. Additionally, N-way ANOVA confirmed that inoculum size and cultivation time are statistically significant for vitamin B12 production, except for inoculum size for co-cultures with *C. jadinii* strains.

4.3.4. Correlation and PCA analysis of co-cultivation on hydrolysate from lignified fibres

The correlation analysis, presented in Figure 26, revealed a strong positive relationship between crude protein, CDW concentration, and pH.

Figure 26: Heatmap of the correlation analysis based on data from co-cultivation trials.

This correlation likely arises from the yeast's ability to deacidify the broth and utilize organic acids and amino acids as nutrient sources. As these compounds are consumed more efficiently, the pH increases. This is a particularly interesting observation, as it suggests that the yeast's capacity for deacidification and organic acid utilization directly influences its growth performance, ultimately positively impacting protein and overall cell mass production. Another

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group of positively correlated samples formed a cluster consisting of free sugars and organic acids, which showed a negative correlation with protein and CDW concentration. This supports the idea that the overall performance of the co-cultures is driven by the robustness of the yeast and its symbiotic relationship with bacteria. The quality of this interaction appears to enhance the utilization of various carbon sources present in the hydrolysate, contributing to the efficiency of the cultivation process.

The exploratory analysis based on PCA was conducted to confirm patterns and trends observed using correlation analysis and to further explore the interrelation between factors. Preliminary investigation of the PCA results showed that PC1 captured 39.5% of the original data variance, while PC2 captured 13.9% of the variance; together, PC1 and PC2 explain more than half of the total variance in the dataset. Exploration of higher components (PC3, PC4) did not provide any useful information, and therefore, they have not been incorporated into this study.

Figure 27 presents the loadings (A) and scores (B) plots for Principal Component 1 (PC1) on the x-axis and Principal Component 2 (PC2) on the y-axis. The loadings plot (Figure 27A) illustrates the original variables as vectors projected onto the PC1 vs. PC2 space. For clarity, each vector is represented as a point marking the tip of the vector. The length and direction of these vectors provide insights into the corresponding variables and their relationships. Notably, pH, CDW concentration, and protein concentration are positioned close to each other, indicating a strong positive correlation, consistent with the findings from the correlation heatmap. Conversely, free sugars and organic acids cluster on the opposite side of the plot, highlighting their negative correlation with CDW and protein concentration. The orientation of the variable vectors in the loadings plot (Figure 27A) corresponds to the distribution of data points in the scores plot (Figure 27B), which represents individual co-culture samples in the PC space. The samples are color-coded based on yeast strain. A distinct separation is observed between *K. marxianus* DSM 70292 and the other yeast strains, and its position in the PC space, farther from CDW and protein concentration than the other strains, justified its exclusion from optimization trials. Overall, the remaining yeast strains exhibit a similar relationship with CDW and protein concentration, as most samples are oriented in the same direction.

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Figure 27: A) PCA loadings (map of variables) for PC1 and PC2; B) PCA scores (map of samples) for PC1 vs PC2 coloured by yeast strain.

To further explore the relationships between pH, protein concentration, and CDW concentration, the PC space was color-coded based on these variables, as shown in Figure 28.

Figure 28: A) PCA scores (map of samples) for PC1 vs PC2 coloured by pH of samples; B) PCA scores (map of samples) for PC1 vs PC2 coloured by protein concentration in samples; C) PCA scores (map of samples) for PC1 vs PC2 coloured by CDW concentration in samples

The visualization provides a clearer understanding of their interconnections. As evident from the figure, samples with higher pH values also exhibit higher protein and CDW concentrations, reinforcing the correlation observed earlier. Based on these findings, Partial Least Squares (PLS) regression and linear modelling were performed to assess the potential for predicting

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protein concentration and CDW concentration using pH as a predictor. However, the resulting models yielded unsatisfactory statistical performance, leading to the abandonment of this approach. Nevertheless, given the strong linear correlations and direct interactions observed between these factors, pH could still be considered a useful qualitative control parameter for providing a rough assessment of co-cultivation performance on halophyte-based hydrolysate.

4.3.5. Mixed cultivation of *L. lactis* and *S. cerevisiae* on hydrolysate from green fibres

In the case of green fibres, sequential fermentation was carried out using hydrolysates obtained from enzymatic hydrolysis (EH) with either acetate buffer as synthetic medium or green juice slurry, as previously described. The cultivation process began with *L. lactis* fermentation for 24 hours, followed by the introduction of *S. cerevisiae* for an additional 48 hours, resulting in a total cultivation period of 72 hours.

The results of this cultivation are presented in Figure 29. It can be observed that microbial growth was consistently higher in samples where green juice slurry was used as the hydrolysis medium, when pre-treatment was applied. These findings are somewhat surprising, given that the highest sugar concentration of 33 g/L was achieved in the hydrolysate derived from pre-treated green fibres using acetate buffer. However, this hydrolysate resulted in the lowest microbial biomass concentration, only 10 g/L, lower than the 13.2 g/L and 13 g/L obtained from non-pre-treated fibres hydrolysed with both synthetic buffer and green juice slurry, respectively. This suggests that the combination of synthetic buffer and pre-treated fibres may have contributed to an inhibitory effect in the hydrolysate, thereby reducing microbial cell formation. Notably, HPLC analysis confirmed that all free sugars were consumed across all samples. In terms of organic acid content, samples processed with green juice slurry contained no detectable acetic or lactic acids, whereas those prepared with synthetic buffer exhibited naturally higher levels of acetic acid. This may have contributed to reduced biomass formation in synthetic buffer-based samples. However, since the hydrolysate produced from raw fibres and acetate buffer did not show similar inhibition, and in fact showed similar trends compared to the green juice slurry, these results suggest that it is the specific combination of synthetic buffer and pre-treated fibres that leads to growth inhibition.

Overall, the highest CDW of 15.2 g/L was achieved with hydrolysate produced from pre-treated fibres and green juice slurry, supporting the use of the slurry as a buffer for hydrolysis in microbial cultivation. This approach enhances the cost-effectiveness of the process by reducing dependence on external inputs while simultaneously achieving higher biomass yields. Interestingly, hydrolysates based on raw fibres also produced relatively high CDW concentrations. Despite the significantly lower sugar content, approximately three times lower,

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carbon utilization may have been more efficient in the hydrolysate based on raw fibres, likely due to the reduced presence of fermentation inhibitors compared to pre-treated fibres.

Figure 29: The results of mixed cultivation on hydrolysates of pre-treated and raw green fibres of *S. ramosissima* with 0.05M acetate buffer and green juice slurry as media. GJ = Green juice; PF = Pre-treated fibres; RF = Raw fibres; AB = Acetate buffer. CWD (cell dry weight) g/L.

4.4. Discussion and conclusion

Initial investigations with six yeast cultures revealed poor nutrient utilization, particularly by *K. marxianus* DSM 70292, *C. jadinii* DSM 70163, and *Y. lipolytica* DSM 8218. In contrast, *K. marxianus* DSM 7238 and *C. jadinii* DSM 2361 demonstrated carbon source utilization but also produced ethanol, which was undesirable in our process. The best-performing yeast was *S. cerevisiae*, which efficiently consumed most carbon sources. However, the fact that C5 sugars were also utilized suggests that naturally present microorganisms in the halophyte juice may have thrived alongside baker's yeast, as the process was not conducted under sterile conditions. The co-cultivation of selected yeasts with *L. plantarum* DSM 13272 and *B. coagulans* ATCC 7050 demonstrated that overall, co-cultures with *B. coagulans* performed better in terms of cell mass, crude protein, and vitamin B12 production. This may be attributed to the fact that *L. plantarum* exhibited better growth compared to *B. coagulans*, leading to elevated lactic acid levels in samples with *L. plantarum*, which in turn inhibited yeast growth. Previous studies have shown that lactic acid and overall organic acids can inhibit yeast growth at certain concentrations (Delmoitié *et al.*, 2025; Narendranath *et al.*, 2001). Notably, statistical analysis revealed that bacterial strains had no significant impact on cell mass or protein production, suggesting that yeast growth is the primary driver of production in bacteria-yeast co-cultures. Moreover, control samples did not show carbon sources utilization or microbial metabolite production, indicating that the naturally present microorganisms were inhibited. However, based on previous experiments with *S. cerevisiae*, where C5 sugars were

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consumed, it is likely that other species coexisted in the hydrolysate during cultivation. It is possible that yeast, acting as a natural detoxifier, reduced harmful compounds or produced growth factors in the hydrolysate, thereby enabling the growth of other microorganisms (Jofre *et al.*, 2021).

The optimization trial yielded excellent results in product formation, with *S. cerevisiae* and *K. marxianus* DSM 7238 performing the best in combination with *B. coagulans*, surpassing the *C. jadinii* strains. The bacteria-yeast co-cultures achieved 17.5 g of CDW, 6.9 g of crude protein, and 42.2 mg of vitamin B12/L of broth with *K. marxianus* DSM 7238, and 16.5 g of CDW, 6.3 g of crude protein, and 47.5 mg of vitamin B12/L of broth with *S. cerevisiae*, respectively. These maximum yields were obtained at the highest inoculum level of 10% (v/v) after 72 hours of cultivation, except for vitamin B12 production with *K. marxianus* DSM 7238. Furthermore, the decreasing concentrations of acetic and lactic acids across all samples, along with a steady pH increase over the cultivation period, indicate active yeast metabolism of these acids, suggesting their potential for effective deacidification in mixed microbial cultures. Notably, in the *K. marxianus* DSM 7238 co-culture, pH significantly increased from 5.13 to 8.41, likely due to yeast shifting towards amino acid consumption once the primary carbon source was depleted, leading to ammonia or urea release and a subsequent pH rise, also known as alkalization (Ljungdahl and Daignan-Fornier, 2012; Ough *et al.*, 1991). Overall, a larger inoculum size 10% (v/v) resulted in higher sugar consumption, greater organic acid utilization, and a more pronounced pH increase compared to lower inoculum sizes. Interestingly, most free sugars were depleted within just 24 hours, particularly in co-cultures with *K. marxianus* DSM 7238 and *S. cerevisiae*. However, cell growth continued beyond 72 hours, suggesting that microbial cultures were utilizing alternative nutrient sources.

The subsequent exploratory analysis confirmed that the performance of the co-culture is primarily influenced by the yeast's ability to deacidify and detoxify the halophyte-based substrate, directly linking the deacidification process to CDW and crude protein production. This highlights yeast robustness as a key factor in product formation. However, compared to sole yeast cultivation on halophyte-based media, the addition of bacteria clearly reduced stress on yeast, resulting in the absence of ethanol production and higher overall product formation. While the exact mechanism behind these interactions remains unknown, it is likely that a symbiotic relationship is established between the introduced cultures, ultimately enhancing their performance in a mutually beneficial way.

The sequential fermentation of enzymatic hydrolysates from *S. ramosissima* green fibres revealed several important insights into the interaction between media composition, pre-treatment, and microbial performance. Although hydrolysates derived from pre-treated fibres using acetate buffer exhibited the highest sugar concentration of 33 g/L, they unexpectedly

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yielded the lowest microbial biomass of 10 g/L. This contrasts with the results from non-pre-treated fibres, which produced higher biomass yields of 13.2 g/L and 13 g/L with synthetic buffer and green juice slurry, respectively. These findings suggest that the combination of synthetic buffer and pre-treated fibres may have produced an inhibitory effect on microbial growth, likely due to compounds generated during pre-treatment that remained in the buffer-based hydrolysate. Interestingly, the inhibitory effect was not observed in raw fibre hydrolysates, even when acetate buffer was used, reinforcing the hypothesis that it is the specific synergy of synthetic buffer and pre-treatment that limits biomass formation. Additionally, the relatively high CDW achieved from raw fibre hydrolysates, despite their low sugar concentrations, suggests efficient carbon utilization and potentially lower inhibitor content. These results emphasize the importance of not only sugar concentration but also hydrolysate composition and origin, and medium compatibility in optimizing microbial growth. To conclude, this study demonstrated the potential of bacteria–yeast co-cultivation for improving microbial growth, nutrient utilization, and postbiotic production on halophyte-based media. Notably, yeast-driven deacidification was identified as a key mechanism improving culture conditions, which in turn promoted microbial activity and increased overall yields. The ability of yeasts to detoxify the substrate likely supported the growth of other beneficial microorganisms, leading to improved fermentation efficiency. The observed microbial interactions suggest a potential for further process optimization and industrial-scale applications in sustainable protein and postbiotic production. Overall, this research highlights the advantages of bacteria–yeast co-cultivation on halophyte hydrolysate in enhancing microbial growth and metabolic output in non-sterile conditions. Future studies should focus on refining cultivation parameters, exploring additional microbial combinations, and assessing large-scale feasibility to further develop a halophyte-based biorefinery.

5. References

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